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The Sainsbury Laboratory

M70X Project Report

Development of a near-isogenic line panel in
barley to stripe rust

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TSL

UEA

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Abstract

Global food production needs to increase by 60-110% by 2050 to meet exponential population growth and changing diets. Moreover, the current environment is having a negative impact on yield; with disease outbreaks are a major source of yield loss, which is further exacerbated by climate change. *Puccinia striiformis* f. sp. *tritici* (*Pst*) causes global losses of wheat equating to a US\$979 million per year. Genetic resistance is the ideal method to combat against persistent and emerging epidemics. A major challenge for breeding durable disease resistance has been the deployment of single major effect host resistance genes that have subsequently broken down in cultivation. Due to increased worldwide threat from *Pst*, and several major epidemics, it is imperative to identify novel sources of resistance (Bryant *et al.*, 2014; Kertho *et al.*, 2015). The vast majority of plants are free of disease and therefore possess durable NHR. Barley is an intermediate host of *Pst*, meaning that very few accessions are susceptible. Previous work has established that nonhost resistance (NHR) in barley to *Pst* is conditioned by natural gene stacks, which may prove more durable than native host resistance genes if reengineered into wheat; an economically important crop. In this project, we aim to isolate multiple resistance loci to *Pst* derived from diverse barley accessions. In total, 18 different *Rps* loci or haplotypes from 14 different donor accessions have been isolated. This work will facilitate rapid fine mapping, map-based cloning, allele mining and subsequent functional analysis.

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List of Abbreviations

APR	Adult plant resistance
<i>Bgt</i>	<i>Blumeria graminis</i> f. sp. <i>tritici</i>
<i>Bgs</i>	<i>B. graminis</i> f. sp. <i>secalis</i>
CC	Coiled-coil
CWR	Crop wild relatives
DAMP(s)	Damage-associated molecular pattern(s)
DTI	DAMP- triggered immunity
ETS	Effector-triggered susceptibility
ETI	Effector-triggered immunity
<i>f. sp.</i>	<i>forma specialis</i> (singular)
<i>ff. spp.</i>	<i>formae speciales</i> (plural)
HTAP	High-temperature adult-plant
IPs	Invasion patterns
IPRs	Invasion pattern receptors
IPTRs	Invasion pattern-triggered responses
MABC	Marker-assisted backcrossing
MAMP(s)	Microbial-associated molecular pattern(s)
MTI	MAMP- triggered immunity
NB-LRR	Nucleotide-binding, leucine rich repeat
NHR	Nonhost resistance
NIL(s)	Near isogenic line(s)
NLR(s)	NB-LRRs and NOD-like receptors

NOD	Nucleotide-binding oligomerization
PAMP(s)	Pathogen- associated molecular pattern(s)
<i>Pgs</i>	<i>Puccinia graminis</i> f. sp. <i>secalis</i>
<i>Pgt</i>	<i>Puccinia graminis</i> f. sp. <i>tritici</i>
PRRs	Pattern recognition receptors
<i>P. striiformis</i>	<i>Puccinia striiformis</i>
<i>Psh</i>	<i>Puccinia striiformis</i> f. sp. <i>hordei</i>
<i>Pst</i>	<i>Puccinia striiformis</i> f. sp. <i>tritici</i>
PTI	PAMP- (PRR-, or pattern-) triggered immunity
<i>R</i>	Seedling resistance
<i>Rps</i>	Stripe rust resistance genes in barley (designated)
<i>Rpst</i>	Stripe rust resistance genes in barley (provisional)
TIR	Toll/interleukin-1 receptor
<i>Yr</i>	Stripe rust resistance genes in wheat

1. Introduction

1. 1. Cereals

Cereals are true grass species (family: Poaceae) cultivated for their edible grain and used as the staple diet for most of the world's population (Moore *et al.*, 1995; Kellogg, 1998; Paterson *et al.*, 2003). Cereal species began to diverge from their common ancestor 50-70 million years ago (MYA) (Paterson *et al.*, 2003), and domestication began approximately 10-12 thousand years ago (Salamini, *et al.*, 2002; Paterson *et al.*, 2003). Many of these domestication events were independent of each other and occurred multiple times; maize (*Zea*) in America; sorghum (*Sorghum*) in Africa; rice (*Oryza*) in Africa and Asia; wheat (*Triticum*), barley (*Hordeum*), rye (*Secale*) and oats (*Avena*) in the Fertile Crescent (Salamini *et al.*, 2002; Paterson *et al.*, 2003; Weiss *et al.*, 2006). These species exhibit a high range of genomic diversity, with 4 to 50 chromosomes and genome sizes between 350 Mb to 17 Gb (Salse *et al.*, 2008).

In 2014, cereals crops produced 2,801M tonnes of grain worldwide. This is split into the major cereal crops, often referred to as the "big three" (Shewry, 2009), with 1,022M tonnes of maize, 741M tonnes of rice and 729M tonnes of wheat. The other minor cereal, in terms of quantity, include 144M, 68M, 28M, 23M, 15M tonnes for barley, sorghum, millet, oats and rye, respectively (<http://faostat3.fao.org/compare/E>). Cereals are the number one staple food crops as they provide approximately half of the world's calories, more than any other type of crop (Borlaug, 1983; Kearney, 2010; Sarwar *et al.*, 2013). Wheat alone provides 20% of calories and 25% of protein consumed by humans (Hubbard *et al.*, 2015).

1. 1. 1. Barley

Barley diverged from wheat and rye between 8 and 9 MYA (Middleton *et al.*, 2014) and can be used as a model species for the Triticeae tribe of Poaceae, which includes wheat, rye and several hundred other species (Soltis and Soltis, 2000; Lü *et al.*, 2015). Modern cultivated barley (*Hordeum vulgare* L.) is a diploid crop species containing seven chromosomes (the primary number of chromosomes in Triticeae) and was domesticated from *H. vulgare* ssp. *spontaneum* (Salamini *et al.*, 2002; IBGSC, 2012). The 5.1 Gb barley (H) genome was published in 2012, using a BAC physical map anchored to a genetic map and enhanced with whole genome shotgun sequencing (IBGSC, 2012). This is comparably smaller to bread wheat's 17 Gb (A, B and D) genomes (IWGSC, 2014) and rye's 8.1 Gb (R) genome (Martis *et al.*, 2013). Barley is also readily transformable which facilitates its use as model species (Lü *et al.*, 2015).

Barley is the fourth most produced cereal crop worldwide, with approximately 75% used for animal feed, 20% used for beverages and the remaining 5% used for food products (IBGSC, 2012). Barley has substantial genetic diversity related to many agronomically important traits such as disease resistance, seasonal habitat, two- and six-rowed, abiotic stress tolerance, yield and earliness (Molnár-Láng *et al.*, 2014). These traits could potentially mitigate the effects of climate change (IBGSC, 2012). Extant landraces show similar genetic composition to 6,000-year-old samples showing that historic diversity can still be accessed (Mascher *et al.*, 2016). However, a major challenge with accessing the genetic diversity of barley for use in wheat is the low crossability of barley in a wheat background (Türkösi *et al.*, 2016). The *Shw* gene (1H) in wheat-barley hybridization lines causes sterility and resulted in only a few wheat/barley introgression lines being developed (Islam, *et al.*, 1981; Tang *et al.*,

2011; Molnár-Láng *et al.*, 2014; Türkösi *et al.*, 2014; 2016). Türkösi *et al.* (2016), most recently produced a set of 10 wheat-barley addition lines in June 2016; these included each chromosome arm minus translocations from 1H (*Shw* locus) and 5H. In contrast, rye has readily been crossed into wheat, with the 1RS.1BL translocation widely used in cultivation (Koebner *et al.*, 1986; Bartoš *et al.*, 2008; Fluch *et al.*, 2012).

1. 2. Disease

Crop diseases threaten global food security with annual losses of 10-16% (Christou, and Twyman, 2004; Strange & Scott, 2005; Oerke, 2006; Hubbard *et al.*, 2015). This yield loss directly threatens the need to increase food production to meet future demands of changing diets and increased population (Parry & Hawkesford, 2010; Mundt, 2014; Cook *et al.*, 2015; Váry *et al.*, 2015; Li *et al.*, 2016). Due to climate change, current projections predict that the three major cereal crops yield will decrease by 9-14% by 2020 (Kole *et al.*, 2015). This is because; the severity of crop diseases will certainly be impacted from changes in temperature, CO₂, precipitation, ozone and UV-B radiation (Váry *et al.*, 2015). Increases in temperature have been shown to accelerate leaf senescence, reduce starch content and yield (Kole *et al.*, 2015) and suppress disease resistance (Zhu *et al.*, 2010). In the case of *Fusarium* head blight and *Zymoseptoria tritici* blotch, both have shown increased severity with increased CO₂ levels (Váry *et al.*, 2015). These effects will be exacerbated by a predicted 8-50% reduction in cropping area (from land degradation, urban expansions and nonfood crops), and a reduction of agricultural inputs of water, fertilisers and pesticides (Tanksley & McCouch & 1997; Váry *et al.*, 2015).

1. 2. 1. Cereal Rusts

Rusts (or rust fungi) (order: Puccinales) are obligate biotrophic fungal pathogens of plants (Hovmøller *et al.*, 2011; Bettgenhaeuser *et al.*, 2014). There are three rust diseases that primarily affect wheat and barley: leaf (brown), stem (black) and stripe (yellow) rust. The fungal pathogen *Puccinia triticina* and *P. hordei* are the causal agents of wheat and barley leaf rust; *P. graminis* of stem rust; and *P. striiformis* of stripe rust, respectively (Horvath *et al.*, 2002; McDonald and Linde, 2002a; Bettgenhaeuser *et al.*, 2014; Woldead *et al.*, 2015).

Leaf rust develops rapidly at warm temperatures (10°C-30°C) and causes small yield loss of 10-30% on wheat (Kolmer, 2013). Stem rust is also called the summer rust due to abundant sporulation towards the end of the growing season, favouring humid and warm temperatures (15°C-35°C). With the capacity to cause 100% loss in a few weeks based on its ability to infect the stem and compromise its integrity, stem rust is universally feared (Singh *et al.*, 2008).

P. striiformis has a host range of 320 grass species across 50 genera, however this may be over estimated by 45% (Hovmøller *et al.*, 2011). It also exhibits both genera and cultivar level specialisation (Hovmøller *et al.*, 2011). Stripe rust is one of the most serious and destructive fungal disease affecting grass species (Line, 2002; Hovmøller *et al.*, 2010; Chen *et al.*, 2014; Li *et al.*, 2016), and is now considered the most damaging cereal rust (Beddow *et al.*, 2015). This is because the pathogen is widespread in all major wheat-producing areas with an expanding geographic range (**Figure 1**) (Beddow *et al.*, 2015). Stripe rust can cause substantial yield loss of up to 100% if infection occurs very early and continues to spread in susceptible cultivars (Chen, 2005; Afzal *et al.*, 2007; Hubbard *et al.*, 2015). In most cases, yield loss ranges from 10-70% depending on the susceptibility, earliness, rate and duration

of infection as well as environmental factors such as temperature and moisture levels (Chen, 2005). Grain quality suffers from reduced nitrogen and therefore protein content (Devadas *et al.*, 2014). Each year, 5.47 million tonnes (0.75%) of wheat is predicted to be lost, equivalent to US\$979 million per year. This is comparatively low when considered up to 88% of wheat production is predicted to be susceptible to stripe rust (**Figure 2**) (Beddow *et al.*, 2015).

Figure 1. The expanding geography of crop losses attributable to stripe rust, before and after 2000: a, Global 1960–1999; b, Global 2000–2012. Data is country-level from Wellings (2011). *Note.* Adapted from Beddow *et al.* (2015).

Figure 2. Modelled global climate vulnerability for stripe rust. Red areas are modelled as being persistently vulnerable to stripe rust; green areas are modelled as being seasonally vulnerable. *Note.* Sourced from Beddow *et al.* (2015).

Stripe rust was originally restricted to cooler temperate climates of 2°C-15°C, or areas of high elevation in tropical regions (Chen, 2005). Since 2000, new strains have emerged, such as *PstS1* and *PstS2* adapted to higher temperatures, expanded virulence repertoires and increased aggression (Markell and Milus, 2008; Ali *et al.*, 2014; Bryant *et al.*, 2014; Hubbard *et al.*, 2015; Hovmøller *et al.*, 2016; Walter *et al.*, 2016). These isolates may represent the most rapid and expansive spread of a pathogen in history and directly resulted in the severe USA and Australia epidemics post 2000. Epidemics also occurred in northern and eastern Africa, western and central Asia and the Middle East in 2009 (Hovmøller *et al.*, 2010). Continued epidemics and the extreme level of susceptibility present in cultivars could result in a worldwide pandemic (Hovmøller *et al.*, 2010; Beddow *et al.*, 2015). The pathogen has a clonal yet highly diverse population structure (Hovmøller *et al.*, 2011). As a result, the combination of both asexual and sexual reproduction systems is hypothesised to be of the highest risk (McDonald and Linde, 2002; Hovmøller *et al.*, 2011). The Himalayan and Near-Himalayan area is suggested to be the putative origin of stripe rust, and the Middle East/East Africa as the source of high temperature-adapted strains (Ali *et al.*, 2014).

1. 2. 2. Stripe Rust

Stripe rust has a macrocyclic (five spore stages), heteroecious (two host) life cycle (Hovmøller *et al.*, 2011; Bettgenhaeuser *et al.* 2014). The primary (asexual) host of stripe rust are cereal species such as wheat or barley, whereas sexual reproduction is completed on the alternate host - barberry (*Barberis* or *Mahonia spp.*) (**Figure 3**) (Jin *et al.*, 2010; Hovmøller *et al.*, 2011; Chen *et al.*, 2014).

On cereal hosts, dikaryotic (two nuclei with haploid genomes) urediniospores are asexually produced through repeated infections of the primary host (**Figure 3a**). Individual uredinia

cluster and produce urediniospores that re-infect and form clustered lesions longitudinally to form the typical stripes. Once senescence of the host plant begins, telia are produced (Figure 3b). These telia produce two cell diploid teliospores, formed from karyogamy. The germinating teliospores produce basidiospores (Figure 3c). These basidiospores can cause pycnia on the upper side of barberry leaves (Figure 3d). This is followed by aecia development on the lower side of the leaf (Figure 3e). The resulting aeciaspores can then successfully infect wheat and produce uredinia, which completes the sexual life cycle (Hovmøller *et al.*, 2011).

Figure 3. Life cycle of *P. striiformis*. Stages on wheat include: a) urediniospores and telial stage, b) clusters of teliospores, c) two celled teliospores germinate with a basidium developing into four basidiospores. Stages on barberry include: d) the pycnial and e) aecial stages. The magnified photo shows three aecia. *Note.* Sourced from Hovmøller *et al.* (2011).

1. 2. 3. Infection Process

Urediniospores germinate (optimum temperature 7-12°C) and enter the intercellular space via the stomata and differentiate into a substomatal vesicle, without forming an appressorium on the leaf surface (**Figure 4**). The substomatal vesicle generally forms 2-3 primary infection hyphae, which develop into the haustorial mother (HM) cells. These HM cells penetrate the plant cell within 24 hours and develop a haustorium, which exists between the plant cell wall and plasma membrane (Hovmøller *et al.* 2011). These haustoria play a vital role in nutrient acquisition and effector signalling (Garnica *et al.*, 2014). The majority of haustoria form in mesophyll cells, with up to 15% present in epidermal cells. The infection continues to spread within the leaf, forming pustules (uredinia) (optimum temperature 12-20°C), which erupt from the leaf releasing thousands of urediniospores (Hovmøller *et al.* 2011; Chen, 2013; Bettgenhaeuser *et al.*, 2014).

Figure 4. Diagram illustrating the infection process of urediniospores through time measured as days post infection (dpi) on a susceptible host. Urediniospores (S) enter the leaf epidermis via the stomata resulting in invaginated haustoria (H) within mesophyll cells at 1 day post inoculation (dpi). Extended infection results in the production of pustules/sporulating uredinia (P) through the epidermis approximately 14 dpi. S, urediniospore; SV, substomatal vesicle; IH, invasive hyphae; HM, haustorial mother cell; H, haustorium; P, pustule; G, guard cell. *Note.* Sourced from Cantu *et al.* (2013).

1. 2. 4. Host Range

In 1894, Eriksson noted that the ability of a fungal isolate to infect another host was dependent on which species it was originally obtained (Tosa, 1992). This became the concept of *formae speciales* (ff. spp.), where morphologically indistinguishable forms of a pathogen were based on host specificity, potentially representing an early stage in evolution (Hovmøller *et al.*, 2011; Bettgenhaeuser *et al.*, 2014). Hybridisation of *formae speciales* of powdery mildew has previously been noted on triticale, based on hybridization of *Blumeria graminis* f. sp. *tritici* (*Bgt*) and *B. graminis* f. sp. *secalis* (*Bgs*) resulted in the formation of *B. graminis* f. sp. *triticales* (Menardo *et al.*, 2016).

P. striiformis f. sp. *tritici* (*Pst*) and *P. striiformis* f. sp. *hordei* (*Psh*) are the causal agents of wheat and barley stripe rust, respectively, although they are known to have overlapping host ranges (**Table 1**) (Chen *et al.*, 1994; Chen, 2005; Wellings, 2011; Bettgenhaeuser *et al* 2014; Derevnina *et al.*, 2015). The host range of *Pst* includes common bread wheat, durum wheat, cultivated and wild emmer wheat and triticale, as well as some accessions of barley and rye (Chen *et al.*, 2014). A second ff. spp. to affect barley species in Australia was identified in 1997 called *P. striiformis* f. sp. *pseudo-hordei* (Chen *et al.*, 2014; Kamino *et al.*, 2016).

Table 1. Different *formae speciales* of *Puccinia striiformis* and their corresponding host specialisations.

Common Name	Formae speciales (<i>ff. spp.</i>)	Species Specialisation	Reference
Wheat stripe rust	<i>P. s. f. sp. tritici</i>	Wheat <i>spp.</i>	Eriksson (1894)
Barley stripe rust	<i>P. s. f. sp. hordei</i>	<i>Hordeum spp.</i>	Eriksson (1894)
Barley grass stripe rust	<i>P. s. f. sp. pseudo-hordei</i>	<i>Hordeum spp.</i>	Wellings (2002)
Rye stripe rust	<i>P. s. f. sp. secalis</i>	<i>Secale spp.</i>	Eriksson (1894)
	<i>P. s. f. sp. elymi</i>	<i>Elymus spp.</i>	Eriksson (1894)
	<i>P. s. f. sp. agropyron</i>	<i>Agropyron spp.</i>	Eriksson (1894)
Cocksfoot stripe rust	<i>P. s. f. sp. dactylidis</i>	<i>Dactylis glomerata</i>	Manners (1960)
	<i>P. s. f. sp. poae</i>	<i>Poa pratensis</i>	Tollenaar (1967)
	<i>P. s. f. sp. leymi</i>	<i>Leymus secalinus</i>	Niu <i>et al.</i> (1991)
	<i>P. s. f. sp. bromi</i>	<i>Bromus carinatus</i>	Niks <i>et al.</i> (2015)

1. 3. Disease Management

There are several methods currently employed to prevent disease outbreaks. Landscape approaches such as removal of alternative host and crop rotation can reduce disease and aid management but is expensive and difficult to implement (Mundt, 2014). Chemicals (pesticides/fungicides) can be applied to control diseases but are expensive, potentially

harmful to the environment and as such, are considered a short-term solution (Line, 2002; Ellis *et al.*, 2015). In contrast, genetic resistance is preferred as it can be reliable, environmentally friendly and cost effective (Hovmøller, 2007; Chen *et al.*, 2013; Huang and Zimmerli, 2014; Li *et al.*, 2016), with US\$32 million per annum economically justified into *Pst* research (Beddow *et al.*, 2015).

However, unlike animals, plants lack mobile defence cells and adaptive immune systems. Plant immunity relies solely on autonomous cell immunity and systemic signals emanating from infection sites (Jones and Dangl, 2006). Firstly, pathogens have to overcome passive defence barriers such as identifying the stomata, overcoming the waxy cuticle and epidermis, or preformed antimicrobial proteins or chemicals (Heath, 2000; Thordar-Christensen, 2003; Bettgenhaeuser *et al.*, 2014). Secondly, active plant immunity is conditioned by a layered receptor repertoire currently accepted as the zigzag model (Jones and Dangl, 2006; Dodds and Rathjen, 2010; Monaghan and Zipfel, 2012; Dangl *et al.*, 2013; Macho and Zipfel, 2014; Cook *et al.*, 2015; Macho and Zipfel, 2015).

1. 3. 1. Genetic Resistance: The Zigzag Model

Microbial- or pathogen-associated molecular patterns (MAMPs or PAMPs), such as flagellin (**Figure 5** and **6**) are recognized by transmembrane pattern recognition receptors (PRRs) expressed on the plant cell surface (Jones and Dangl, 2006; Bettgenhaesuer *et al.*, 2014). If the PAMP is detected, PAMP- (PRR-, or pattern-) triggered immunity (PTI) (or MAMP-triggered immunity (MTI)) prevents further colonisation (Jones and Dangl, 2006; Macho and Zipfel, 2014; Cook *et al.*, 2015; Tang and Zhou, 2016). PRRs initiating PTI are predominately receptor-like kinase or receptor-like proteins (Greeff *et al.*, 2012; Win *et al.*, 2012) and can be divided into early (1-30 min post pathogen attack) or late defence responses (Albert,

2013). This is achieved through generation of ethylene and/or reactive oxygen species (ROS burst), activation of mitogen-activated protein kinases and immune-related genes, and/or deposition of callose in the cell wall (Albert, 2013; Macho and Zipfel, 2014; Macho and Zipfel, 2015). Damage-associated molecular patterns (DAMPs), such as polysaccharides released by damaged host cell walls can also trigger a plant response (Zipfel, 2009; Albert 2013; Macho and Zipfel, 2014). These are released when cells are under a microbial attack and initiate a DAMP- triggered immunity (DTI) response (Zipfel, 2009; Bettgenhaeuser *et al.*, 2014; Tang and Zhou, 2016).

Figure 5. The zigzag model illustrates the layered receptor repertoire of active plant defence immunity. In the first phase pathogen-associated molecular patterns (PAMPs) trigger PAMP- triggered immunity (PTI). In the second phase, pathogen effectors can suppress immunity to cause ETS. In the third phase, a single effector can be recognized to cause effector-triggered immunity (ETI). Note. Sourced from Jones and Dangl (2006).

PTI can be suppressed by effectors (also called virulence factors) that are secreted into plant cells via haustorial cells of fungi/oomycetes (Jones and Dangl, 2006; Dangl *et al.*, 2013;

Garnica *et al.*, 2014; Macho and Zipfel, 2015). These effectors can cause the pathogen to become virulent by suppressing PTI to cause effector-triggered susceptibility (ETS) (Jones and Dangl, 2006; Macho and Zipfel, 2015; Du *et al.*, 2016).

Detection of cytoplasmically localised effectors is predominately performed by nucleotide-binding, leucine rich repeat (NB-LRR) domain proteins (also known as nucleotide-binding oligomerization (NOD)-like receptors, both referred to as NLRs) (Bernoux *et al.*, 2016; Khan *et al.*, 2016; Sukarta *et al.*, 2016). Multiple additional protein domains for NLRs have been elucidated (Bent, 1996; Ellis *et al.*, 2000; Sharma *et al.*, 2014; Kroj *et al.*, 2016; Sarris *et al.*, 2016). Common domains include Toll/interleukin-1 receptor (TIR) and coiled-coil (CC) that are used in the signalling response (Bernoux *et al.*, 2011; Cesari *et al.*, 2014; Bernoux *et al.*, 2016). Detection of apoplastic effectors is recognized by PRRs (Win *et al.*, 2012). This results in effector-triggered immunity (ETI). ETI is an accelerated and amplified PTI response that is associated with the hypersensitive response (HR), usually involving programmed cell death (Jones and Dangl, 2006). This restricts infection by biotrophs and hemi-biotrophs and confers resistance to the plant (Jones and Dangl, 2006; Thomma *et al.*, 2011; Gill *et al.*, 2015). These same receptors can act as susceptibility factors for necrotrophic pathogens, which deliberately induce cell death for nutrient acquisition (Dobón *et al.* 2015).

Figure 6. Different classes of pathogens express PAMPs and MAMPs as they colonize a plant. Plants detect these via extracellular PRRs and initiate PAMP triggered immunity (PTI; step 1). Pathogens can deliver virulence effectors to the plant cell apoplast to block PAMP/MAMP detection (not shown) and to the plant cell cytoplasm (step 2). These effectors are directed to specific subcellular locations where they can suppress PTI and facilitate virulence (step 3). Intracellular NLR receptors can detect effectors in three principal ways: (1) by direct receptor ligand interaction (step 4a; gene-for-gene); (2) by detecting effector-mediated alteration in a decoy protein (no other function) that structurally mimics an effector target (step 4b; decoy model); or (3) by sensing effector-mediated alteration of a host virulence target (step 4c; guard model). NLR activation results in effector triggered immunity (ETI; step 5). *Note.* Sourced from Dangl *et al.* (2013).

There are currently four modes of action through which NLRs can activate a defence response. The gene-for-gene relationship (**Figure 6, 4a**) proposed by Flor states that R proteins (encoded by *R* genes), predominately NLRs interact directly with avirulence proteins (encoded by *Avr* genes) of the pathogen (Flor, 1971; Hammand-Kosack and Jones, 1997; Van Der Biezen and Jones, 1998; McDowell and Woffenden, 2003). The guard model (**Figure 6, 4b**) proposed by van der Biezen and Jones (1998) suggests that an R protein (the guard) interacts with a second plant protein (the guardee) that is modified by a pathogen effector (Dangl and Jones, 2001; McDowell and Woffenden, 2003; van der Hoorn and Kamoun, 2008). The decoy model (**Figure 6, 4c**) proposed by van der Hoorn and Kamoun (2008) involves a protein that specialises in the perception of pathogen effectors, trapping the effector in a recognition event. This “decoy”, “bait” or “trap” protein may evolve through duplication of effector targets but serve no function in pathogen development or resistance (van der Hoorn and Kamoun, 2008; Khan *et al.*, 2016). The fourth mode is a combination of the direct gene-for-gene model and the decoy model, termed integrated domain (Cesari *et al.*, 2014; Sarris *et al.*, 2016). In this model, an “integrated decoy” domain is fused into an NLR; this forms a complex with a second NLR to initiate defence signalling (Cesari *et al.*, 2014; Kroj *et al.*, 2016). Thomma *et al.* (2011) argued this PTI-ETI dichotomy to be a continuum as it only defines resistance based on the receptor involved. This resulted in the development of the invasion model (Cook *et al.*, 2015).

1. 3. 2. Genetic Resistance: The Invasion Model

The Zigzag model narrowly defined the plant immune response and is restricted to biotrophic pathogens (Cook *et al.*, 2015). It implied that ETI occurred after PTI by specific receptor classes. It also fails to account for the type of reaction such as host and nonhost

resistance (Cook *et al.*, 2015). The invasion model expands the zigzag model and currently encompasses all known models of disease resistance (**Figure 7**), removing the divide between PRRs and NLRs (Cook *et al.*, 2015). Invasion patterns of the microbe encompass PAMPs and effectors into a continuum of structural or functional characteristics as well as whether they highly conserved or race specific (Cook *et al.*, 2015). Therefore all detectable ligands are termed invasion patterns (IPs), which are recognized by a variety of IP receptors (IPRs), and in turn results in IP-triggered responses (IPTRs) (Cook *et al.*, 2015). Resistance genes were originally defined as any gene that conferred resistance to a pathogen and therefore included NLRs and PRRs (Hammand-Kosack and Jones, 1997; McDowell and Woffenden, 2003; Dodds and Rathjen, 2010; Bernoux *et al.*, 2011; Dangl *et al.*, 2013). This transitioned to and currently only incorporates NLRs, which are pathogen race specific and effective at all plant growth stages: known as seedling resistance (Ellis *et al.*, 2014; Cook *et al.*, 2015).

Figure 7. Comparison of the zigzag model to the invasion models. a, the zigzag model is defined in strict terms where microbe-associated molecular patterns (MAMPs; yellow box) are recognized by pattern recognition receptors (PRRs) resulting in MAMP-triggered immunity (MTI), or effectors (red box) by R proteins resulting in effector-triggered immunity (ETI). b, Some molecules do not fit into these strict terms and therefore a continuum in the invasion model is used to represent this. Invasion patterns (IPs) are the ligands that are perceived by plant IP receptors (IPRs), resulting to IP-triggered response(s) (IPTR(s)). *Note.* Sourced from Cook *et al.* (2015).

1. 3. 3. Seedling and Adult Plant Resistance

Seedling (also known as: all-stage, major, monogenic, single, vertical, gene-for-gene, race specific) resistance (*R*) genes are considered pathogen race-specific and predominantly encode NLRs. Some *R* genes have been referred to as broad spectrum, however this may be down to the number of races being tested (Ellis *et al.*, 2014). They also may not confer complete resistance, where smaller sized and/or quantity of pustules form, called “incomplete” resistance. It is important to note this has often previously been associated

with “partial” resistance in the literature. This described a range of different plant-pathogen systems, confounding the definition further (Ellis *et al.*, 2014).

Adult plant resistance (APR) is often considered non-race specific, which provides broad-spectrum resistance (Ellis *et al.*, 2014). This confers an intermediate phenotype of resistance called “partial” (also known as: polygenic, multi-gene, quantitative or horizontal) resistance (Paloix *et al.*, 2009; Poland *et al.*, 2009; St. Clair, 2010; Mundt, 2014; Gill *et al.*, 2015). Some APR genes provide resistance to all isolates, while others provide resistance to multiple pathogens (Ellis *et al.*, 2014). This is seen in the multiple pathogen recognition specificity of the *Lr34* in wheat, which confers resistance to powdery mildew, stripe rust and leaf rust resistance (Krattinger *et al.*, 2011). APR genes encode a heterogeneous range of proteins including PRRs, ABC transporters such *Yr36* (Fu *et al.*, 2009), or weak NLRs (St. Clair, 2010; Ellis *et al.*, 2014). High-temperature adult-plant (HTAP) resistance, a subset of adult plant resistance is induced when temperatures increase and plants mature (Yan and Chen, 2007b; Chen *et al.*, 2013), such as *Yr36* (Fu *et al.*, 2009). There is currently no consistent distinction between *R*, APR and HTAP resistance genes in nomenclature (Ellis, *et al.*, 2014).

All genes can breakdown after their introduction to commercial cultivation because they are often deployed as single genes. This allows pathogens to easily evolve away from recognition through mechanisms such as novel virulence, modified effectors or loss of effectors (Johnson 1978; Johnson, 2000; Ellis *et al.*, 2014). Many single resistance genes undergo a “boom” and “bust” cycle; where a gene of large effect is distributed over a wide geographic area. Resulting in widespread suppression of disease (the “boom”), and the pathogen evolves to overcome the resistance from the higher selection pressure after time, resulting in widespread incidence of disease (the “bust”) (McDonald and Linde, 2002; Brown

and Tellier, 2011). Several genes deployed together (gene stack) are often considered more durable as multiple genetic barriers have to be overcome at once (Castro *et al.*, 2009; Palloix *et al.*, 2009; Poland *et al.*, 2009; St. Clair, 2010; Burdon *et al.*, 2014; Mundt, 2014; Gill *et al.*, 2015; Kertho *et al.*, 2015).

1. 3. 4. Durable Resistance

Durable resistance is defined as the widespread and prolonged use of resistance, in an environment favourable to the pathogen, yet remains effective (Johnson, 1981; Johnson, 1984). As stated before, APR genes are often considered more durable (Palloix *et al.*, 2009; Poland *et al.*, 2009; St. Clair, 2010; Mundt, 2014; Gill *et al.*, 2015); however the validity of this statement is in debate as the definition of durability makes no reference to the underlying genetic control and some examples disprove this theory (St. Clair, 2010; Lo Iacono *et al.*, 2013). Such as in the case of *P. graminis*, some barley cultivars were susceptible to both wheat and rye isolates of stem rust (*P. graminis* f. sp. *tritici* (*Pgt*) and *graminis* f. sp. *secalis* (*Pgs*), respectively) (Green, 1966; Bettgenhaeuser *et al.*, 2014). Resistance to *Pgt* in barley was mapped to the *Rpg1* locus (Brueggeman *et al.*, 2002). This single gene provided durable resistance for approximately 50 years from the mid-1940s (Horvath *et al.*, 2002; Leonard and Szabo, 2005).

To breed for durable resistance, firstly the mechanisms conferring resistance (*R*, APR, HTAP), their deployment strategy and the process of evolution of the target pathogen must be considered (McDonald and Linde, 2002; Jones and Dangl, 2006; Mundt, 2014). Generally, the deployment strategy of resistance loci is vital to ensure their maximum durability and consists of five approaches including national landscape approaches, gene rotations, cultivar mixtures, one by one, or gene stacks (McDonald and Linde, 2002; Mundt, 2014). Disease

epidemics have previously been associated with the composition of cultivars in a region (Papaix *et al.*, 2011), i.e. many farmers growing the same cultivar in an area mimics a narrow genetic base. However, the cost, coordination and labour required implementing national approaches or gene rotations is often unfeasible (Mundt, 2014). Cultivar mixtures have been shown to suppress disease and hinder epidemics (**Figure 8**) but do not completely prevent the disease (Jones, 2001; Dangl and Jones, 2001). Additionally, downstream processing of grain often requires certain varieties, limiting the use of cultivar mixtures (Swanston *et al.*, 2000). Deploying single resistance loci is only appropriate in small areas or unfavourable environments (McDonald and Linde, 2002; Mundt, 2014). Based on this information, gene stacks are seen as the most cost effective method of genetic resistance (Burdon *et al.*, 2014; Mundt, 2014).

Figure 8. In a cultivar (*R*) mixture, the number of released spores travelling to the nearest susceptible cultivar is considerably lower when compared to a monoculture by lowering the density of susceptible plants (dilution effect). Additionally, a proportion of the spores released from an infected plant (inoculum source) are removed from the population by failing to infect resistant plants (barrier effect). *Note.* Sourced from Jones (2001).

Natural gene stacks also allow mitigation over potentially higher risk pathogens. The risk of pathogens is dependent on the evolutionary mechanisms of mutation rate, population size, gene flow, reproduction, mating systems and natural selection. The primary source of genetic variation is mutation, generating new alleles that could potentially breakdown resistance loci. Larger populations have comparably more mutants; this in turn reduces the chance of alleles being lost or fixed by random genetic drift (McDonald and Linde, 2002). The pathogen dispersal mode directly affects gene flow, for example the airborne dispersal of *Pst* allows spores to travel across continents (McDonald and Linde, 2002; Chen *et al.*, 2014). This allows populations to gain novel alleles or re-merging alleles. Mixed (sexual and asexual) reproduction, such as in *Pst* is hypothesised to pose the highest risk (**Figure 9**) as it provides maximum redistribution of alleles within a population. New combinations of alleles (genotypes) are rapidly generated from the sexual cycle and successful genotypes can be propagated through the asexual cycle. Outcross mating of the sexual cycle poses a greater risk than inbreeding as more combinations can be generated. Directional selection imposed by major resistance loci in cultivation increases the frequency of virulent strains resulting in the “bust” of resistance loci (McDonald and Linde, 2002).

Breeding techniques have traditionally only selected for a single resistance locus and integrated this resistance over successive generations (Johnson, 1984; Wolfe 1985; Pink, 2002; Mundt, 2014). However, with the widespread use of an *R* gene in modern monoculture, this has often resulted in the “boom” and “bust” cycle alluded to earlier (McDonald and Linde, 2002b; Brown and Tellier, 2011; Dangl *et al.*, 2013; Huang and Zimmerli, 2014). Modern breeding approaches that facilitate access to a wider range of genetic diversity include the use of marker-assisted selection (MAS) to introgress resistance

loci (Collard *et al.*, 2005; Rommens *et al.*, 2007; Collard and Mackill, 2008; Jones *et al.*, 2009; Kole *et al.*, 2015).

Figure 9. The interaction between reproduction and mating cycle of a pathogen determines the evolutionary risk of its population. Note. Sourced from McDonald and Linde (2002a).

This wider genetic diversity is present within crop wild relatives (CWR) and landraces. They represent a substantial reservoir of natural gene stacks that can be useful in breeding durable resistance (Dangl *et al.*, 2013) and overcome the genetic bottleneck that occurred during domestication (Tanksley and McCouch, 1997). To introgress CWR or landrace loci, generation of near isogenic lines (NILs) is the preferred method (**Figure 10**). This is because CWRs also possess undesired characteristics that would be introgressed into the elite cultivars (Hospital, 2005; Jones *et al.*, 2009; Bergelson & Roux, 2010; Piquerez *et al.*, 2014; Kole *et al.*, 2015). The development of NILs can be performed through phenotypic selection and backcrossing. Alternatively, the use of markers in marker-assisted backcrossing (MABC) in NIL production can accelerate NIL development by (1) tracking traits that are difficult to phenotype (e.g. expense, time, or complex inheritance; (2) tracking life stage specific traits

(such as APR genes (Ellis *et al.*, 2014)); (3) reduce the number of backcrosses required; and (4) stacking multiple major loci traits (Miedaner & Korzun, 2012). This method has the potential to track natural or novel gene stacks (Rae, *et al.*, 2006, Miedaner & Korzun, 2012). These genes can be categorized into host or nonhost resistance depending on the susceptibility of the donor species (Bettgenhaeuser *et al.*, 2014).

Figure 10. Development of a near-isogenic line (NIL). Parental lines are crossed to produce an F₁ generation, which is repeatedly backcrossed to a single parent (recurrent parent; red) to introgress a desired region into a certain genetic background (E.g. “Blue” trait in a “red” genetic background). Note. Adapted from Bergelson & Roux (2010).

1. 3. 5. Host and Nonhost Resistance

As the majority of plants are disease free, only a limited number of pathogens can cause infection. The host range of a pathogen is defined by which plant species the pathogen can complete its life cycle on (Bettgenhaeuser *et al.*, 2014; Macho and Zipfel, 2014). The host range of a pathogen has previously been associated with their phylogenetic distance of host targets (Gilbert and Webb, 2007). If a pathogen can avoid or suppress detection, the pathogen is adapted (Bettgenhaeuser *et al.*, 2014; Macho and Zipfel, 2014). Resistance to pathogens that are non-adapted (i.e. cannot avoid or suppress detection) is known as nonhost resistance (NHR), and therefore the most common type of resistance (Tosa, 1989, 1992; Heath, 2000; Bettgenhaeuser *et al.*, 2014). NHR has the most potential to provide

durable resistance, as effectors delivered to nonhost plants are not sufficient to suppress inducible defences (Niks and Marcel, 2009; Bettgenhaeuser *et al.*, 2014). Tosa (1989) suggested only a few segregating *R* genes confer NHR in plant species closely related to the host species.

NHR is defined as the observation of all genotypes of a species that are resistant to all known isolates of a pathogen and often results in a HR at the infection site (Sentil-Kumar and Mysore, 2013; Piquerez *et al.*, 2014; Bettgenhaesuer *et al.*, 2014). However, in reality not all plant species fall into host (fully susceptible) or nonhost (complete immunity) classes for three reasons: (1) only a few accessions are immune to the pathogen; (2) only a few isolates can infect the plant species; and (3) the spectrum of disease phenotypes of a plant (Bettgenhaeuser *et al.*, 2014; Dawson *et al.*, 2015). Bettgenhaeuser *et al.* (2014) proposed a continuum along a host-nonhost spectrum (**Figure 11**). In intermediate nonhosts, the pathogen can overcome initial defences to form infection but cannot complete its life cycle. In an intermediate host, the pathogen can only form pustules on a small number of accessions to complete its life cycle. Barley is therefore considered an intermediate host of *Pst* and harbours multiple natural gene stacks to wheat stripe rust (Dawson, 2015). This could be used as a novel source of resistance loci in wheat. However, transfer of these loci will most likely be dependent on a transgenic method. To facilitate this, loci need to be isolated, fine mapped and cloned.

Figure 11. Model for transition from host to nonhost spectrum. A, The incidence of life cycle completion (pustule) of a nonadapted pathogen decreases faster than incidences of colonisation. B, Pustule formation frequency and C, colonisation frequency define host systems, intermediate host systems, intermediate nonhost systems, and nonhost systems. Note. Sourced from Bettgenhaeuser *et al.* (2014).

1. 3. 6. Genetic Resistance to Stripe Rust

In total, there are 55 stripe stripe rust resistance (*Yr*) genes catalogued in wheat that are derived from wheat or interspecific hybrids; these include 41 *R* genes and 14 APR/HTAP genes (Chen *et al.*, 2013; Chen *et al.*, 2014; Kertho *et al.*, 2015). Due to the increasing worldwide threat from *Pst*, and several major occurrences of resistance breaking down, it is imperative to identify novel sources of resistance (Bryant *et al.*, 2014; Kertho *et al.*, 2015). Therefore, the aim of this project is to generate a genetic resource to unravel the genetic architecture conferring NHR to *Pst* in barley and its relationship to *Psh* resistance. The long-term goal is to reengineer these loci into commercially important crops, such as wheat (Dawson *et al.*, 2016). This strategy has been previously utilised in barley to identify NHR to *Pgt* isolate Ug99, which has identified eight loci (Mamo *et al.*, 2015).

A total of 26 loci were identified to confer resistance to *Psh* in barley (Chen and Line, 1999; Nover and Scholz, 1969), with 21 under recessive mode of inheritance and five under dominant mode of inheritance (Chen and Line, 2003, Chełkowski et al, 2003). Only five of these loci were designated (first five in **Table 2**). Characterisation of functional overlap with *Pst* resistance is incomplete, with only *rps2* known to function against both *Psh* and *Pst* (**Table 2**). Currently, 52 loci have been identified to confer resistance to *P. striiformis sensu lato* (all isolates) in barley. Of these, only seven have been anchored to the barley genetic map: *rps1* (Yan and Chen, 2007a); *rps2* (Dawson, 2015); *Rps4* (Nover and Scholz 1969); *rps5* (Yan and Chen, 2006); *Rps6* (Dawson et al, 2016; Li et al, 2016), *Rps7* and *Rps8* (Dawson, 2015).

Previous work from the Moscou group (The Sainsbury Laboratory, UK) has designated three major *R* genes conferring intermediate host resistance to *Pst*: *Resistance to P. striiformis 6* (*Rps6*, =*Rpst2*); *Rps7* (= *Rpst1*); and *Rps8* (= *Rpst3*), which map to chromosomes 7HL, 1HS and 4HL, respectively (**Table 2** and **Figure 12**). All three loci provide resistance to *Pst*: however *Rps6* and *Rps7* restrict colonization, whereas *Rps8* prevents pustule formation (Dawson, 2015). *Rps6* (7H), *Rps7* (1H), and *Rps8* (4H) map nearby or to powdery mildew resistance genes: *Mlf* (potential coupling), *Mla* (complete coupling), and *mlo* (uncoupled) loci, respectively (Schönfeld et al., 1996; Büschges et al., 1997; Wei et al., 1999), but no functionality against *Psh* has been noted (**Table 1**).

Rps6 was recently isolated and fine mapped to a 0.1 cM region of 7HL by Dawson *et al.* (2016) and 0.14 cM region by Li *et al.* (2016). The locus contains three NLRs, *NLR-A*, *NLR-D*, and *NLR-E*. *NLR-D* is expressed in the roots whereas *NLR-A* and *NLR-E* in the leaves (Matt Moscou, pers. comm.). *Rps7* has been shown to be in complete coupling with *Mla* (*Mla7*

and *Mla8*) (Dawson, 2015). The *Mla3* locus has also been shown to confer resistance to rice blast (*RMo1*) and victorin sensitivity produced by necrotroph Victoria blight (*HvLOV*) (Inukai *et al.*, 2006; Lorang *et al.*, 2010). Stem rust resistance (*Sr33* and *Sr50*) genes are also shown to be in complete coupling with *Mla* (Periyannan *et al.*, 2013; Mago *et al.*, 2015). The *Mla* locus has the capacity to recognize powdery mildew, wheat stripe rust, stem rust and rice blast resistance, as well as susceptibility to Victoria blight depending on the *Mla* allele. *Rps8* has been recently fine mapped to a 0.3 cM region (Bettgenhaeuser and Moscou, unpublished).

Table 2. Designated stripe rust resistance genes in barley accessions[#].

Locus	Synonym	<i>Psh</i> ^a	<i>Pst</i> ^a	Donor Accession	Chr. ^b	Arm ^b
<i>rps1</i>	<i>yr</i>	Y	ND	HOR 2926 (=BBA 2890; <i>rps1.a</i>); Bigo (<i>rps1.b</i>); Mazurka (<i>rps1.c</i>); Abyssinian 14	3H	L
<i>rps2</i>	<i>yr2</i>	Y	Y	Abed Binder 12	2H	L
<i>rps3</i>	<i>yr3</i>	Y	ND	I 5	ND	ND
<i>Rps4</i>	<i>Yr4</i>	Y	N	Cambrinus; Heils Franken; Astrix; Deba Abed; Europa	1H	S
<i>rps5</i>	<i>rpsGZ</i>	Y	ND	Grannelose Zweizeilige	4H	L
<i>Rps6</i>	<i>Rpst2</i>	N	Y	Abed Binder 12; Bowman; Baronesse; Golden Promise	7H	L
<i>Rps7</i>	<i>Rpst1</i>	N	Y	CI 16153; Golden Promise	1H	S
<i>Rps8</i>	<i>Rpst3</i>	N	Y	Abed Binder 12; Baronesse; Duplex; Golden Promise; HOR 1428; Morex; Sultan 5; Baronesse and several others	4H	L
<i>Rps9</i>	<i>RpstHOR1428-2</i>	Y	Y	HOR 1428	5H	L
<i>Rps10</i>		Y	ND	WBDC085	5H	L

[#]Data compiled from Chen and Line (1999, 2003); Chełkowski *et al.* (2003); Safavi *et al.* (2013a), Safavi *et al.* (2013b) and Matt Moscou (pers. comm.). Additional loci can be found in Chełkowski *et al.* (2003) and Pahalawatta and Chen (2005).

^a Y, functional against ff. spp; N, non-functional against ff. spp; ND, not determined.

^b ND, not determined; L, long arm; S, short arm

Figure 12. Consensus genetic map of known *Psh* and *Pst* resistance loci in barley.

1. 4. Project Objectives

The objectives of this project is as follows:

- Development of a near-isogenic line (NIL) panel as a genetic resource
- Isolation of resistance loci within a universally susceptible genetic background
- Assess the functional overlap against *Psh* and *Pst*
- Initiate fine mapping of most advanced loci

To understand the genetic architecture conferring intermediate host specificity, the underlying gene at each locus must be isolated for fine mapping and map-based cloning.

Two issues currently prevent progress: (1) the number of loci present in accessions (**Table 3**) and (2) colocalisation with additional pathogen resistance loci. This poses the question: whether loci are pleiotropic by having multiple pathogen recognition or are closely linked.

With an increasing number of *R* genes, the number of individuals required to isolate a gene in an F_2 population expands exponentially. For example, three *R* genes would require a minimum of 64 individuals, whereas four *R* genes would require a minimum of 256 individuals based on probability. With many accessions containing multiple *R* loci, it becomes unfeasible to provide sufficient mapping resolution. Therefore, the development of a NIL panel is required to isolate these loci. Each of the donor accession's resistance loci will be introgressed into a genetic background known as the recurrent parent. The recurrent parent cv. Manchuria will be used, as it is universally susceptible to *Psh* and *Pst*. The NIL panel will resolve the two critical issues of the number of loci and colocalisation of resistance genes in accessions. In addition, the panel will facilitate rapid fine mapping, map-based cloning, novel allelic variant discovery and assess the relationship between closely related loci (Matt Moscou, pers. comm.). Resistant accessions are selected based on their phenotypic response when challenged with *Pst* to elucidate novel genes or alleles.

Table 3. Current NIL development using a diverse set of germplasm with multiple disease resistance loci.

Donor Parent (Male)	Recurrent Parent (Female)	Resistance Loci				Backcross generation
		Stripe Rust		Powdery Mildew ^a	Rice Blast ^a	
		Barley (<i>Psh</i>) ^a	Wheat (<i>Pst</i>) ^a			
Abed Binder 12	Manchuria	•	•••			BC ₄
Heils Franken	Manchuria	••	••	•		BC ₄
Bowman	Manchuria	•	•••	•		BC ₃
CI16153	Manchuria		•	•		BC ₃
CIho 4196	Manchuria		•	•		BC ₃
HOR 1428	Manchuria	•	•••••			BC ₃
WBDC085	Manchuria		•••	•		BC ₃
Sultan 5	Manchuria		••	•		BC ₃
Baronesse	Manchuria	•	••	•	•	BC ₂
BCD12	Manchuria		•			BC ₁
Benton	Manchuria	•	•			BC ₁
CI16139	Manchuria			•		BC ₁
Duplex	Manchuria		•••			BC ₁
Morex	Manchuria		••			BC ₁
Russell	Manchuria		•			BC ₁

^aDots indicate the number of resistance loci conferring resistance to corresponding pathogen

2. Methods and Materials

2. 1. Plant Materials and Backcrossing Schema

Due to the nature of this project as being on going, backcross populations are at various stages throughout the backcrossing scheme, ranging from BC₁ to BC₄ (**Table 3**). Each accession is backcrossed to cv. Manchuria as the recurrent parent (female). This accession was selected based on its universal susceptible status to *Psh* and *Pst* isolates from the United Kingdom. Resistant lines were selected if they contained known and unknown resistance architectures, with additional genes potentially uncovered during NIL development. Marker-assisted backcrossing (MABC) was used to accelerate the programme to remove donor genetic background. Seed for resistant lines Abed Binder 12 (PI 327961), Baronesse (PI 568246), Benton (PI 539105), Bowman (PI 483237), CI16139 (CIho 16139), CI 16153 (CIho 16153), Honan wang ta mai (CIho 4196; PI 64275), Duplex (PI 290343), Heils Franken (PI 290183), HOR 1428 (PI 328669), Morex (CIho 15773), Russell, (PI 483127) and susceptible line Manchuria (CIho 2330) were obtained from the United States Department of Agriculture Germplasm Resources Information Network (USDA-GRIN). BCD12, Sultan 5 and WBDC085 were obtained from Patrick Hayes (Oregon State University, Oregon, USA), Ralph Panstruga (Aachen University, Germany), and Brian Steffenson (University of Minnesota, Minnesota, USA), respectively. Resistant lines are crossed as the paternal pollen donor to the recurrent maternal parent Manchuria to produce F₁ populations. F₁ progeny are crossed to the maternal parent again to begin the backcrossing programme. This is done through manual emasculatation of cv. Manchuria, removing all three anthers from florets before anther dehiscence has occurred. The ear can be pollinated 2-4 days post emasculatation. Manual pollination involves removal the ear from the donor parent and

removal of the awns and top of the florets. Heat and warm air is applied to stimulate anther dehiscence. The ear is inverted and rotated around the recurrent parent ear to release pollen into the open recurrent florets. F₂ populations can be produced at any backcross stage for phenotypic screens using pathogen assays.

Figure 13. Backcrossing schema to generate a NIL panel. An F₁ population is obtained from crossing the resistant donor and susceptible recurrent parent. Backcross (BC) stages are produced from repeated backcrossing to the susceptible recurrent parent; this is accelerated using marker-assisted backcrossing selection. An F₂ population can be produced for phenotypic screens at any BC stage for phenotypic screens.

2.2. Fungal Materials and Assays

Pst isolate 08/21 and *Psh* isolate B01/2 were used for pathogen assays. The National Institute of Agricultural Botany collected these isolates in 2001 and 2008, respectively. *Pst* isolate 08/21 and *Psh* isolate B01/2 were bulked and maintained on susceptible wheat cv. Solstice and barley cv. Cassata, respectively. Isolates must be maintained on susceptible lines, as the pathogen cannot be cultured on artificial media (Chen *et al.*, 2014; Hubbard *et al.*, 2015). For pathogen assays, plants are sown in 1 L peat-based compost pot. Plants are grown in a controlled environment room (CER) at 18°C day and 11°C night using a 16 h light and 8 h dark cycle with lighting provided by metal halide bulbs (Philips MASTER HPI-T Plus 400 W/645 E40). Seedlings are inoculated at 14 days after sowing, which coincides with the emergence of the first leaf but prior to the second leaf. Fresh urediniospores are mixed at a 1:16 weight ratio with talcum powder. The inoculum is disseminated over the seedlings on a spinning platform using a compressed air pump. Seedlings are sealed in plastic bags and stored in the dark at 6°C to achieve the high humidity required for germination. After 48 – 72 h post inoculation, seedlings are returned to the CER (Dawson *et al.*, 2016).

2. 3. Macroscopic Phenotyping

Macroscopic phenotyping was undertaken on seedlings 14 days post-inoculation (dpi). *Pst* inoculation was scored on a dual discrete nine-point scale from 0 to 4, with increments of 0.5 for both chlorosis (leaf yellowing) and infection (pustule formation). A score of 0 indicates 0% coverage of the phenotype and a score of 4 indicates 100% coverage (Dawson *et al.*, 2015). The McNeal scale is used to phenotype *Psh* inoculated plants. The scale is designed for host systems and ranges from 0 (immune; no infection) to 9 (very susceptible; abundant pustules without chlorosis) in integer increments (McNeal, 1971).

2. 4. Molecular Genotyping

DNA extraction was performed in 96-well plate format, modified from Pallotta *et al.* (2003) for low-quality gDNA or a CTAB-based method, modified from Stewart and Via (1993) for high-quality gDNA. Both extraction methods use 4 cm² leaf tissue. All genotyping utilised KASPTM marker technology, performed by the John Innes Centre Genotyping Service. SNPs were initially selected at approximately 40 cM intervals, for approximately five markers per chromosome or 35 per genome plus additional markers to flank the donor regions. Extra markers are required to ensure polymorphism between all parent lines. A total of 501 KASP markers have been developed from the barley oligonucleotide pool assay (BOPA) (**Figure 14**) (Close *et al.*, 2009).

The Kompetitive Allele Specific PCR (KASPTM) system uses two forward primers overlapping the point mutation, with unique tail sequences and one reverse primer. In the first round of PCR, the primer matching the point mutation (allele) present in the DNA can bind, elongating the target region. In the second round, the reverse primer elongates the complementary strand. In subsequent rounds, the number of incorporated tails (specific to the allele present) increases, releasing the fluorophore from the tail quencher to generate signal. This fluorescent signal is analysed to determine genotype, homozygous for either allele or heterozygous for both alleles (Lister *et al.*, 2013). SNPs were converted into KASP markers using a similar approach as described in (Ramirez-Gonzalez *et al.*, 2015). The KASP primer mix was prepared by mixing 12 µL VIC primer (s1), 12 µL FAM primer (s2), 30 µL reverse primer (r), and 46 µL dH₂O. KASP PCR reactions contained 2µL gDNA (~10-20 ng), 2 µL KASP V4.0 2x master mix, and 0.055 µL primer mix. KASP PCR cycling used an initial denaturation step at 95°C for 15 minutes followed by touchdown PCR cycling consisting of

ten cycles of 94°C for 20 seconds, and annealing step of 65°C for 25 seconds decreasing by 1°C each cycle. Samples then cycled 30 times at 94°C for 20 seconds and annealed at 57°C for 1 minute before being held at 4°C.

Figure 14. A total of 501 KASP™ markers (black) have been developed from barley OPA markers (grey) (460 KASP markers shown). Each string represents a chromosome, with 1H in the centre and 7H on the outside anchored by the centromere. Grey bars represent 10 cM.

2.5. Progeny Selection

Individual plants were selected based on their genotypic profile and phenotypic resistance if used. Genotypic selection utilised KASP marker technology to assess the percentage of recurrent parent. Individual plants that contain the loci of interest and the highest percentage of recurrent cv. Manchuria genotype were selected.

2. 6. Genetic Map Construction

Genetic maps are constructed using Mapmaker QTX (Manly *et al.*, 2001) or JoinMap v4 (van Ooijen, 2006) with varying numbers of KASP markers depending on polymorphisms between the original biparental cross and the loci of interest. Default parameters and independence LOD threshold of 4.0 was used to construct the linkage groups. The Kosambi mapping function was used to estimate genetic distances.

2. 7. QTL and ANOVA Analyses

QTL Cartographer (v1.17j) was used to perform composite interval using model 6, a step size of 2 cM, and a window size of 10 cM. The Eqtl module was used to extract significant QTLs under the H₀:H₃ model using experiment-wide thresholds (EWT) that were calculated using 1,000 permutations with the reselection of background markers using a threshold of $\alpha < 0.05$ (Doerge and Churchill, 1996, Lauter *et al.*, 2008). ANOVA analyses for testing the linkage of individual markers were performed with R/qtl.

3. Results

3. 1. Backcrossing Overview

The aim of this project was to initiate the isolation of multiple resistance loci into a universal susceptible barley accession. Barley accessions (in **Table 3**) were challenged with *Pst* isolate 08/21 to assess wheat stripe rust resistance. Macroscopic phenotyping revealed that Manchuria exhibited susceptibility and was selected as the recurrent parent, whereas resistant lines had phenotypic scores between 0 and 1.5 for chlorosis and 0 for infection. Resistant lines were used as donor accessions. Multiple loci were identified in each accession indicating a large array of resistance loci present in barley. A total of 27 loci and/or haplotypes (**Figure 15**) were entered into the backcrossing schema from 14 donor accessions with a total of 25 loci isolated in a Manchuria genetic background.

The project spans from BC₁ to BC₄ stages. Several accessions were established prior to the start of this project from two completed crossing seasons. The crossing block only used markers flanking loci of interest with accessions Abed Binder and Heils Franken the most advanced. During the project, an additional two crossing seasons were complete utilising MABC and phenotypic selection on the majority accessions. Further donor accessions were also incorporated into the crossing block each season. This allowed additional loci to be isolated on an accelerated timescale. When phenotypic selection was applied, markers were used to confirm susceptibility of accessions that were monomorphic in the region of interest. MABC was used to assess the genetic composition of accessions, to preferentially select higher proportions of recurrent parent while retaining resistance.

Genetic maps were developed for a subset of BC_x families as a genome wide scan for QTLs. These rough genetic maps utilized BOPA1-derived KASP markers every 10-40 cM across the

genome. QTL analysis was performed using composite interval mapping using macroscopic chlorosis and infection (pustule formation) phenotype scores. Initial QTL analysis allowed QTL identification to chromosome or arm level. Marker saturation at the region allowed the development of closely linked flanking markers to be used in MABC.

A total of seven different *Mla* haplotypes have been isolated in the Manchuria genetic background, two functional haplotypes against *Pst* from CI 16153 and CIho 4196; and five unique haplotypes without a known mildew resistance from Bowman, Heils Franken, HOR 1428, Sultan 5, WBDC085. In addition, four haplotypes of *Rps6* have been isolated from Abed Binder 12, Baronesse, Bowman and WBDC085. *Rps8* has been isolated from Sultan 5, Baronesse, Morex and in progress with Duplex, as well as *Rpst10* from HOR 1428 and Heils Franken. Remaining isolated loci include *rps2* from Abed Binder 12, *Rps9* from HOR 1428, *Rps10* in WBDC085, *Rpst7* from Duplex, *Rpp1* from Baronesse and *Mlg* from CI 16139 (**Figure 15**). This translates to 18 loci functional against *Pst*, with two in progress and seven loci against powdery mildew or other pathogens.

Figure 15. Backcrossing history to isolate loci from a variety of resistant donor accessions using a combination of flanking markers, marker-assisted backcrossing and/or phenotypic selection. Discrepancies exist from Table 3, as not all loci have been isolated.

3. 2. Discovery and Isolation of Novel Loci

A sample of the loci isolated using this backcrossing scheme are presented here to illustrate the rapid timescale loci can be isolated. These loci presented are predominantly the most advanced loci within the backcrossing schema and highlight the most intriguing findings of the project.

3. 2. 1. *Rpst10* in Heils Franken

Heils Franken is a German cultivar currently known to harbour *Rps4* and *RpsHF* against *Psh*, and two unknown *Rps* genes against *Pst*, one hypothesized to be *Rps7/Mla*. Heils Franken was hypothesized to harbour an allele of the *Rps7/Mla* locus based on marker segregation in a BC₂F₂ population (**Figure 16**). This allele (*RpstHF*) was isolated in a Manchuria genetic background using MABC. Marker saturation utilising 30 KASP markers and QTL analysis identified critical recombination events in the region at the BC₃ stage. The QTL is located on chromosome 1HS at 1.2 cM on the consensus map with the cosegregating marker SCRI_RS_66630 (**Figure 17, left**). All heterozygous individuals (H genotype; presence of allele) possess *Pst* resistance. All monomorphic Manchuria individuals (A genotype; recurrent susceptible parent) were susceptible to *Pst*. The *Mla* marker MLA_206_p1, mapping to 10.59 cM on the consensus map, showed incomplete segregation with phenotypic scores (highlighted by the red circles; **Figure 17, right**). This novel locus has been provisionally designated *Rpst10*, accounting for 90% ($p < 0.005$) of phenotypic variation with a LOD score of 12.01 (**Table 4**). The *Mla* haplotype of Heils Franken was identified as *Mla37* based on RNAseq, and does not contribute to *Pst* resistance. Both *Rpst10* and *Mla37* have been progressed to BC₄ stage (**Figure 15**). The BC₃F₂ phenotypic screen did not resolve the mapping position locus beyond original recombination events identified at the BC₃ stage.

Figure 16. Phenotype by genotype plot for *Mla* in a Manchuria x Heils Franken BC₂F₂ population inoculated with *Pst.* A, Manchuria; H; Heterozygous; B, Heils Franken.

Figure 17. Phenotype by genotype plot for markers delineating critical recombination event with the *Mla* locus in a Manchuria x Heils Franken BC₃ population inoculated with *Pst.* A, Manchuria; H; Heterozygous.

Table 4. Full model ANOVA table for *Rpst10* of 24 individuals from a Manchuria x Heils Franken BC₂F₂ population using *Pst* isolate 08/21 and McNeal scale.. DF, degrees of freedom; SS, sum of squares; MS, mean squares; LOD, logarithm of odds; % Var, percent of phenotypic variation explained.

	DF	SS	MS	LOD	% Var	<i>p</i> -value (χ^2)	P value (F)
Model	1	42.53	42.53	12.01	90.02	<0.005	<0.005
Error	22	4.71	0.21				
Total	23	47.24					

3. 2. 2. *Rpst10* in HOR 1428

HOR 1428 is an Ethiopian landrace currently known to harbour five different loci, four effective against *Pst* and three against *Psh*, potentially exhibiting functional overlap for recognition of these two pathogens. These include *Rps8* (*Pst* only), *RpsHOR1428-1* (currently *Psh* only), *RpsHOR1428-2*, *RpsHOR1428-3*, and is hypothesised to contain *Rps7/Mla* (*Pst* only). A total of four loci were identified in barley accession HOR 1428 using *Pst* isolate 08/21. These loci were mapping and associated with the *Mla* (allele *RpstHOR1428-1H*) on 1H, *Rps8* on 4H, *RpsHOR1428-2* on 5H and *RpsHOR1428-3* on 6H. During the isolation of *RpstHOR1428-1H* into Manchuria, critical recombinants were identified in the flanking regions surrounding *Mla* locus at BC₂ stage. Marker saturation utilising 54 KASP markers and QTL analysis identified critical recombination events distal to the *Mla* locus. The QTL is located on chromosome 1HS at 1.2 cM on the consensus map with the cosegregating marker SCRI_RS_66630 (**Figure 18, left**). The *Mla* marker MLA_206_p1, mapping to 10.59 cM on the consensus map, showed incomplete segregation with phenotypic scores (highlighted by the red circles; **Figure 18, right**). This QTL has also been provisional designated *Rpst10*, accounting for 71.08% ($p < 0.005$) of phenotypic variation with a LOD score of 6.19 (**Table 5**). Both *Rpst10* and the HOR 1428 allele at the *Mla* locus have been

progressed to BC₃ stage (Figure 15). The BC₂F₂ phenotypic screen did not refine the locus any further and is not included.

Figure 18. Phenotype by genotype plot for markers delineating critical recombination event with the *Mla* locus in a Manchuria x HOR 1428 BC₂ population inoculated with *Pst*. A, Manchuria; H; Heterozygous.

Table 5. Full model ANOVA table for *Rpst10* of 24 individuals from a Manchuria x HOR 1428 BC₂F₂ population using *Pst* isolate 08/21 and McNeal scale. DF, degrees of freedom; SS, sum of squares; MS, mean squares; LOD, logarithm of odds; % Var, percent of phenotypic variation.

	DF	SS	MS	LOD	% Var	P value (χ^2)	P value (F)
Model	1	32.14	31.14	6.19	71.08	<0.005	<0.005
Error	21	13.08	0.62				
Total	22	45.22					

3. 2. 3. *RpsHO1428-5H* in HOR 1428

Chen and Line (2002) originally identified the *RpsHOR1428-5H* locus as *RpsHOR1428-2*, a *Psh* resistance gene, and subsequently as *Rps9* by Kitcher (2016). From two BC₁ families the locus was mapped to KASP marker 1_0292_120_F at 139.63 cM on the consensus map

(**Figure 19**). This was hypothesised to be conferring *Pst* resistance. Through MABC with HOR 1428, the region containing *Rps9* (marker 1_0292_120_F) in a BC₂ individual was found to be monomorphic Manchuria but retained resistance to *Pst* 08/21. A QTL analysis mapped the locus to 162.98 cM on the consensus 5HL map with peak marker 1_1216_68_F (**Figure 19**). The 2-LOD support interval of the QTL spans a 33 cM interval, as well as the genotype by phenotype plot indicating incomplete segregation with phenotype and the markers used (highlighted by the red circles; **Figure 20**). Further marker saturation is required to resolve the locus and obtain more closely linked markers. The 2-LOD support interval indicates two separate regions on 5HL confer *Psh* and *Pst* resistance, respectively (**Figure 19**). The QTL for *Pst* resistance accounts for 47.45% ($p < 0.005$) of phenotypic variation with a LOD score of 13.12 (**Table 6**). The *RpsHOR1428-5H* locus has been progressed to BC₂ stage (**Figure 15**).

Figure 19. Two-LOD support interval of two BC₁F₂ populations (A and B) inoculated with *Psh* isolate B01/2 and one BC₂F₂ population (C) inoculated with *Pst* isolate 08/21 across a 60 cM region on chromosome 5HL. Aligned to the consensus map (green chromosome) developed by Muñoz-Amatriaín *et al.* (2011) with markers annotated in black horizontal lines, and peak markers listed. Blue boxplot and lines, 2-LOD and 1-LOD support intervals; red line, peak marker.

Figure 20. Phenotype by genotype plot for *RpsHO1428-5H* (1_1216_68_F) in a Manchuria x HOR 1428 BC₂F₂ population inoculated with *Pst*. A, Manchuria; H; Heterozygous; B, HOR 1428.

Table 6. Full model ANOVA table for *Rps10* of 94 individuals from a Manchuria x HOR 1428 BC₂F₂ population using *Pst* isolate 08/21 and dual scale by Dawson (2015). DF, degrees of freedom; SS, sum of squares; MS, mean squares; LOD, logarithm of odds; % Var, percent of phenotypic variation explained.

	DF	SS	MS	LOD	% Var	p -value (χ^2)	P value (F)
Model	2	144.76	72.38	13.12	47.45	<0.005	<0.005
Error	91	160.25	1.76				
Total	93	305.11					

3. 2. 4. *Rps10* in WBDC085

WBDC085 is a wild barley accession (part of the Wild Barley Diversity Collection (WBDC) from Jordan (Ames *et al.*, 2015), and was previously found to harbour *Rps6*. During the backcrossing scheme, a novel locus was identified on chromosome 5H, designated as *Rps10*. The KASP marker 2_1141_120_F at 167.9 cM on the consensus map was identified as the most closely linked marker at BC₂ stage. At subsequent BC₂F₂ stage, the peak marker shifted

to 1_0902_120_F at 155.45 cM on the consensus map. This marker shows incomplete segregation with phenotypic scores (highlighted by the red circles; **Figure 21**). The QTL for *Pst* resistance accounts for 26.6% ($p < 0.005$) of phenotypic variation with a LOD score of 6.31 (**Table 7**). The *Rps10* locus has been progressed to BC₃ stage (**Figure 15**).

Figure 21. Phenotype by genotype plot for *Rps10* (1_0902_120_F) in a Manchuria x WBDC085 BC₂F₂ population inoculated with *Pst*. A, Manchuria; H; Heterozygous.

Table 7. Full model ANOVA table for *Rps10* of 94 individuals from a Manchuria x WBDC086 BC₂F₂ population using *Pst* isolate 08/21 and dual scale by Dawson (2015). DF, degrees of freedom; SS, sum of squares; MS, mean squares; LOD, logarithm of odds; % Var, percent of phenotypic variation explained.

	DF	SS	MS	LOD	% Var	p -value (χ^2)	P value (F)
Model	2	70.04	35.02	6.31	26.60	<0.005	<0.005
Error	91	193.28	2.12				
Total	93	263.32					

3. 3. Additional Populations of Interest

3. 3. 1. Abed Binder 12

Abed Binder 12 is a Danish cultivar that is known to harbour *rps2*, *Rps6*, *Rps8* (Table 2). It also possesses a mildew and stripe rust susceptible allele of *Mla/Rps7*. Through the backcrossing scheme; both *rps2* and *Rps6* have been isolated into a Manchuria genetic background to BC₄ stage (Figure 15). Both *rps2* and *Rps6* provide complete resistance in isolation (Figure 22), whereas *Rps8* markers exhibits incomplete segregation of resistance, (highlighted by red circles; Figure 22) this is because markers utilised at BC₁ stage were linked, but not in complete coupling with the locus.

Figure 22. Phenotype by genotype plot for *rps2*, *Rps6*, and *Rps8* in a Manchuria x Abed Binder 12 BC₁ population inoculated with *Pst*. A, Manchuria; H; Heterozygous.

3. 3. 2. Baronesse

Baronesse is a German feed variety (Castro *et al.*, 2012), harbouring *Rps6* and *Rps8* against *Pst*. The *Mla3* allele at *Mla* is not functional against to *Pst*, however it confers resistance to barley powdery mildew (*Blumeria graminis* f. sp. *hordei*; *Mla*) and rice blast (*Magnaporthe oryzae*; *RMo1*), and sensitivity to the victorin toxin from Victoria blight (*Cochliobolus victoriae*; *HvLOV*) on 1HS. Baronesse also possesses resistance to *Phytophthora palmivora* (*Rpp1*) on 5H. However, *Rpp1* is located in a region experiencing complete segregation distortion within the BC₁ population tested, such that the Baronesse allele is always transferred through pollen. Due to the segregation distortion, isolations of *Rps6*, *Rps8* and *Mla3* also carry a heterozygous 5HS chromosome progressed to the BC₂ stage (**Figure 15**). Only the *Rpp1* isolation on 5H, progressed to BC₂ stage, lacks any additional donor material but still segregation distortion on 5HS (**Figure 15**).

4. Discussion

4. 1. Backcrossing Overview

Previously no *Rps* genetic loci had been isolated into a common universal susceptible accession. In total, we have isolated 27 loci: 18 loci functional against *Pst*, with two in progress and seven against powdery mildew or other pathogens. This project illustrates the advantages of the backcrossing scheme to rapidly identify and isolate loci into a desired genetic background, in this case the barley cv. Manchuria, a universal susceptible accession to stripe rust. Markers can be developed rapidly both from barley OPA and RNAseq-derived SNPs. The use of KASP marker technology allows the backcrossing scheme to be flexible to increase or decrease marker quantity to either saturate regions, track loci, or allow polymorphism on additional parental lines entered into the crossing block. MABC can be used to rapidly accelerate breeding programmes, where individuals can be preferentially selected for the recurrent parent (i.e. individuals with a higher proportion that are homozygous recurrent (**Figure 23**)).

With further backcrossing, novel loci are often identified as the removal of major loci can reveal other loci that are potentially masked by other loci such is the case with *Rps10*. Alternatively, novel loci can be discovered through marker saturation of predicted regions such, such as *Rpst10* mapping distal to *Rps7/Mla*. The NIL panel can begin facilitating the rapid fine-mapping and map-based cloning of *Rps* genes. Previously only *rps1* (Yan and Chen, 2007a); *rps2* (Dawson, 2015); *Rps4* (Nover and Scholz 1969); *rps5* (Yan and Chen, 2006); *Rps6* (Dawson et al, 2016; Li et al, 2016), *Rps7* and *Rps8* (Dawson, 2015) had been anchored to the genome, with *rps2* (Dawson, 2015) and *Rps6* fine-mapped (Dawson et al,

2016; Li et al, 2016). To date, no *Rps* genes have been cloned from barley. As the NIL panel continues to expand, more loci can be integrated into map-based cloning pipeline.

BC₂ population

Figure 23. Theoretical distribution of heterozygosity at the BC₂ stage if a, no selection is applied or b, selection is applied in recurrent parent direction.

4. 2. Discovery and Isolation of Novel Loci

4. 2. 1. Heils Franken

QTL analyses of the Heils Franken genetic map revealed two major loci conferring intermediate host resistance to *Pst* isolate 08/21. The *Mla* locus was hypothesized to be the locus conferring *Pst* resistance. Through repeated backcrossing and identification of critical recombinants, the *Pst* resistance was mapped distal to *Mla* (10 cM) at 1.2 cM on chromosome 1H consensus map. This is a novel locus previously not identified by Chen and Line (2002) or Nover and Scholz (1969), and has been provisionally designated as *Rpst10*. Several reasons may explain why *Rpst10* was not previously identified, as the locus does not function against *Psh* isolates. Alternatively, *Rps4* (1HS, unmapped) may have masked the effect of *Rpst10* due to linkage on 1HS. This work shows the *Mla* haplotype present in Heils Franken is not functional against *Pst*. Instead a locus mapping distal to *Mla* confers

resistance. This work highlights the substantial reservoir of resistance loci present within the intermediate host barley.

4. 2. 2. HOR 1428

QTL analyses of the HOR 1428 genome revealed four QTLs functional against *Pst* isolate 08/21, these included *RpsHOR1428-5H* (not *Rps9*; previously identified as *RpsHOR1428-2* by Chen and Line (2002), *RpsHOR1428-3*, *Rps8* and *Rpst10*. *RpsHOR1428-1*, previously identified by Chen and Line (2002), was not functional against *Pst* isolate 08/21. *Rpst10* maps distal to *Mla* with the same segregating marker as Heils Franken. It is therefore currently hypothesised to be the same locus present in Heils Franken. Further recombination screens to fine map both loci will resolve this.

The *RpsHOR1428-5H* locus requires further marker refinement to establish a more closely linked marker due to the large QTL interval. Current results confirm that the locus conferring *Pst* resistance in the BC₂-10 line is not the *Rps9* originally hypothesised, as the region is monomorphic for Manchuria (susceptibility) in this backcross accession. The peak marker currently maps in close proximity on the consensus map to *Rps10* locus present in WBDC085. The current working hypothesis is that the *RpsHOR1428-5H* locus conferring *Pst* resistance is allelic to *Rps10*. Access to previous BC stages is required to isolate and phenotypically screen *Rps9*, to determine whether the locus is functional against *Pst*, without the presence of *Rps10* interfering.

4. 2. 2. WBDC085

Identification of the *Rps10* locus again highlights the advantages of the backcrossing scheme to identify and isolate novel loci, as well as highlighting the substantial reservoir of *Rps* genes present in barley accessions. The most closely linked marker 1_0902_120_F for

Rps10, does not completely segregate with phenotypic scores and therefore is not in complete coupling. Further marker saturation is required to delineate the boundary of *Rps10*. However, the 5H locus present in both HOR 1428 and WBDC085 map in close proximity to each other. The *RpsHOR1428-5H* present in HOR1428 is hypothesised to be *Rps10*, originally identified in WBDC085. Further work is required to isolate the *Rps6* locus present in WBDC085.

4. 3. Additional Populations of Interest

4. 3. 1. Abed Binder 12

Abed Binder 12 harbours a substantial number of *Rps* genes. The backcrossing scheme has isolated *rps2* and *Rps6* (**Figure 15**). This should facilitate the map-based cloning of these loci as they are already fine mapped (Dawson, 2015; Dawson *et al.*, 2016; Li *et al.*, 2016). Access to prior BC populations will facilitate the isolation of *Rps8* and/or other loci yet to be identified. *Rps8* markers showed incomplete segregation with phenotypic resistance, this is because utilised markers at BC₁ stage were not in complete coupling with the locus. Marker saturation of the region will establish more closely linked markers. The negative allele of *Rps7* may also prove advantageous to isolate to elucidate which mutation(s) inactivate the *R* gene.

4. 3. 3. Baronesse

Baronesse has been identified to harbour the *Mla3* allele at *Mla*. This does not provide resistance to *Pst*, however it provides multiple pathogen recognition against powdery mildew (*Mla*) and rice blast (*RMo1*), and sensitivity to the victorin toxin from Victoria blight (*HvLOV*) on 1HS. This provides a unique opportunity to investigate the mechanisms that control multiple pathogen recognition. However, genomic conflict between the genomes of

Baronesse and Manchuria leads to complete segregation distortion of the 5HS chromosome, resulting in only Baronesse alleles being transmitted to the offspring during backcrossing. This complicates mapping of resistance genes, as additional resistance genes may be present. This indicates a pre-zygotic barrier is preventing transmission of the Manchuria alleles, as all seeds are viable. Manchuria had previously been associated with a lethal progeny (*Lep1*) gene when crossed to cv. Deficiens that may colocalise with this region (Wiebe, 1934). All seedlings failed to germinate (known as hybrid necrosis), where combinations of deleterious alleles result in extreme fitness penalties such as hybrid lethality (Bomblies and Weigel, 2007). Investigation of the multiple pathogen recognition would be dependent on identifying alternative cultivars harbouring *Mla3*, using an alternative recurrent parent, or a three-way cross to eliminate the genome conflict on 5HS between Baronesse and Manchuria. Meanwhile, the Baronesse by Manchuria backcross lines will provide useful information into the segregation distortion of 5HS. The *Rps6* and *Rps8* isolations can be used as secondary sources for map-based cloning.

4. 4. Future Developments

This backcrossing scheme can be used for the isolation of further loci, such as the remaining loci present in accessions already being utilised (e.g. Abed Binder 12) or in accessions previously not utilised (e.g. Benton or Golden Promise). Genotyping-by-sequencing (GBS) could be utilised at later stages of NIL production to assess and remove any remaining donor genetic material (Pea *et al.*, 2013).

Previously no *Rps* genetic loci had been isolated into a common universally susceptible accession. The advantage of using Manchuria, as the recurrent parent is two-fold: (1) Manchuria is susceptible to *Psh* and *Pst* isolates and (2) Manchuria is a historic cultivar.

Universal susceptibility will facilitate the assessment of functional overlap between loci against isolates of *Pst* and *Psh*, as well as powdery mildew (Moseman, 1972). Functional overlap is known to occur at *rps2* locus, effective against *Psh* and *Pst*. However functional overlap does not occur in *Rps4*, *Rps6*, *Rps7* and *Rps8*. After final NILs are produced, this *Rps* diversity panel could be used for race profiling different stripe rust isolates to assess compatibility, without the complication of background *Rps* loci interfering with phenotypic assessment. The data collected could inform breeding programmes, by selecting combinations of *Rps* genes that will be effective in their target environment. Additionally, as Manchuria is a historic cultivar, generation of each NIL can be used as pre-breeding material to introgress loci into future elite barley cultivars.

In terms of transferring resistance to wheat, either cytogenetic methods such as crossing to addition lines developed by Türkösi *et al.* (2016), or transgenic methods could be applied. For transgenic methods, map-based cloning of *Pst* resistance is required to insert the locus into a vector. This could provide substantial benefit to wheat breeding as a source of novel and potentially durable wheat stripe rust resistance in Africa, the Americas, Asia and Australia.

4. 5. Conclusion

The generation of the NIL panel has isolated 18 different loci or haplotypes of *Rps* loci from 14 donor accessions. This was accelerated using MABC to preferentially select on the recurrent parent genotype. This provides a NIL panel of isolated *Rps* genes that will facilitate their fine-mapping and map-based cloning. The long-term goal of this project is to assess and potentially reengineer barley *Pst* resistance in an economically important crop such as wheat. This may provide a stronger and/or more durable disease resistance against wheat

stripe rust. This could allow breeding programmes to incorporate this novel material to generate novel gene stacks that could indirectly increase yields, as well as reduce costs such as landscape practices or pesticides/fungicide treatments.

5. References

- Albert M (2013) Peptides as triggers of plant defence. *Journal of Experimental Botany* 64:5269-5279
- Ali S, Gladieux P, Leconte M, Gautier A, Justesen AF, Hovmøller MS, Enjalbert J, de Vallavieille-Pope C (2014) Origin, Migration Routes and Worldwide Population Genetic Structure of the Wheat Yellow Rust Pathogen *Puccinia striiformis* f.sp. *tritici*. *PLoS Pathog* 10:e1003903
- Ames N, Dreiseitl A, Steffenson BJ, Muehlbauer GJ (2015) Mining wild barley for powdery mildew resistance. *Plant Pathology* 64:1396-1406
- Bartoš J, Paux E, Kofler R, Havránková M, Kopecký D, Suchánková P, Šafář J, Šimková H, Town CD, Lelley T, Feuillet C, Doležel J (2008) A first survey of the rye (*Secale cereale*) genome composition through BAC end sequencing of the short arm of chromosome 1R. *BMC Plant Biology* 8:95-95
- Beddow JM, Pardey PG, Chai Y, Hurley TM, Kriticos DJ, Braun H-J, Park RF, Cuddy WS, Yonow T (2015) Research investment implications of shifts in the global geography of wheat stripe rust. *Nature Plants* 1:15132
- Bent AF (1996) Plant Disease Resistance Genes: Function Meets Structure. *The Plant Cell* 8:1757-1771
- Bergelson J, Roux F (2010) Towards identifying genes underlying ecologically relevant traits in *Arabidopsis thaliana*. *Nat Rev Genet* 11:867-879
- Bernoux M, Ellis JG, Dodds PN (2011) New insights in plant immunity signaling activation. *Current opinion in plant biology* 14:512-518

- Bernoux M, Burdett H, Williams SJ, Zhang X, Chen C, Newell K, Lawrence GJ, Kobe B, Ellis JG, Anderson PA, Dodds PN (2016) Comparative Analysis of the Flax Immune Receptors L6 and L7 Suggests an Equilibrium-Based Switch Activation Model. *The Plant Cell* 28:146-159
- Bettgenhaeuser J, Gilbert B, Ayliffe M, Moscou MJ (2014) Nonhost resistance to rust pathogens – a continuation of continua. *Frontiers in Plant Science* 5
- Bomblies K, Weigel D (2007) Hybrid necrosis: autoimmunity as a potential gene-flow barrier in plant species. *Nat Rev Genet* 8:382-393
- Borlaug NE (1983) Contributions of Conventional Plant Breeding to Food Production. *Science* 219:689-693
- Brown JKM, Tellier A (2011) Plant-Parasite Coevolution: Bridging the Gap between Genetics and Ecology. *Annual Review of Phytopathology* 49:345-367
- Brueggeman R, Rostoks N, Kudrna D, Kilian A, Han F, Chen J, Druka A, Steffenson B, Kleinhofs A (2002) The barley stem rust-resistance gene Rpg1 is a novel disease-resistance gene with homology to receptor kinases. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences of the United States of America* 99:9328-9333
- Bryant RRM, McGrann GRD, Mitchell AR, Schoonbeek H-j, Boyd LA, Uauy C, Dorling S, Ridout CJ (2014) A change in temperature modulates defence to yellow (stripe) rust in wheat line UC1041 independently of resistance gene Yr36. *BMC Plant Biology* 14:1-10
- Burdon JJ, Barrett LG, Rebetzke G, Thrall PH (2014) Guiding deployment of resistance in cereals using evolutionary principles. *Evolutionary Applications* 7:609-624

- Büschges R, Hollricher K, Panstruga R, Simons G, Wolter M, Frijters A, van Daelen R, van der Lee T, Diergaarde P, Groenendijk J, Töpsch S, Vos P, Salamini F, Schulze-Lefert P (1997) The Barley *Mlo* Gene: A Novel Control Element of Plant Pathogen Resistance. *Cell* 88:695-705
- Castro A, Chen X, Hayes PM, Johnston M (2009) Pyramiding Quantitative Trait Locus (QTL) Alleles Determining Resistance to Barley Stripe Rust: Effects on Resistance at the Seedling Stage. *Crop Science* 43:651-659
- Castro AJ, Gamba F, German S, Gonzalez S, Hayes PM, Pereyra S, Perez C (2012) Quantitative trait locus analysis of spot blotch and leaf rust resistance in the BCD47 × Baronesse barley mapping population. *Plant Breeding* 131:258-266
- Cesari S, Bernoux M, Moncuquet P, Kroj T, Dodds PN (2014) A novel conserved mechanism for plant NLR protein pairs: the ‘integrated decoy’ hypothesis. *Frontiers in Plant Science* 5
- Chełkowski J, Tyrka M, Sobkiewicz A (2003) Resistance genes in barley (*Hordeum vulgare* L.) and their identities with molecular markers. *Journal of Applied Genetics* 44:291-309
- Chen XM (2005) Epidemiology and control of stripe rust *Puccinia striiformis* f. sp. *tritici* on wheat. *Canadian Journal of Plant Pathology* 27:314-337
- Chen FQ, Prehn D, Hayes PM, Mulrooney D, Corey A, Vivar H (1994) Mapping genes for resistance to barley stripe rust (*Puccinia striiformis* f. sp. *hordei*). *Theoretical and Applied Genetics* 88:215-219
- Chen W, Wellings C, Chen X, Kang Z, Liu T (2014) Wheat stripe (yellow) rust caused by *Puccinia striiformis* f. sp. *tritici*. *Molecular Plant Pathology* 15:433-446

- Chen X (2013) Review Article: High-Temperature Adult-Plant Resistance, Key for Sustainable Control of Stripe Rust. *American Journal of Plant Sciences* 4:20
- Chen X, Coram T, Huang X, Wang M, Dolezal A (2013) Understanding Molecular Mechanisms of Durable and Non-durable Resistance to Stripe Rust in Wheat Using a Transcriptomics Approach. *Current Genomics* 14:111-126
- Chen X, Line RF (1999) Recessive Genes for Resistance to *Puccinia striiformis* f. sp. *hordei* in Barley. *Phytopathology* 89:226-232
- Chen X, Line RF (2003) Identification of genes for resistance to *Puccinia striiformis* f. sp. *hordei* in 18 barley genotypes. *Euphytica* 129:127-146
- Christou P, Twyman RM (2004) The potential of genetically enhanced plants to address food insecurity. *Nutrition Research Reviews* 17:23-42
- Close TJ, Bhat PR, Lonardi S, Wu Y, Rostoks N, Ramsay L, Druka A, Stein N, Svensson JT, Wanamaker S, Bozdogan S, Roose ML, Moscou MJ, Chao S, Varshney RK, Szűcs P, Sato K, Hayes PM, Matthews DE, Kleinhofs A, Muehlbauer GJ, DeYoung J, Marshall DF, Madishetty K, Fenton RD, Condamine P, Graner A, Waugh R (2009) Development and implementation of high-throughput SNP genotyping in barley. *BMC Genomics* 10:1-13
- Collard BCY, Jahufer MZZ, Brouwer JB, Pang ECK (2005) An introduction to markers, quantitative trait loci (QTL) mapping and marker-assisted selection for crop improvement: The basic concepts. *Euphytica* 142:169-196
- Collard BCY, Mackill DJ (2008) Marker-assisted selection: an approach for precision plant breeding in the twenty-first century. *Philosophical Transactions of the Royal Society B: Biological Sciences* 363:557-572

- Cook DE, Mesarich CH, Thomma BPHJ (2015) Understanding Plant Immunity as a Surveillance System to Detect Invasion. *Annual Review of Phytopathology* 53:541-563
- Dangl JL, Jones JDG (2001) Plant pathogens and integrated defence responses to infection. *Nature* 411:826-833
- Dangl JL, Horvath DM, Staskawicz BJ (2013) Pivoting the Plant Immune System from Dissection to Deployment. *Science (New York, NY)* 341:10.1126/science.1236011
- Dawson, A. M. (2015). Elucidating the molecular genetics of host and nonhost resistance in barley to stripe rust. *PhD Thesis*. University of East Anglia.
- Dawson AM, Bettgenhaeuser J, Gardiner M, Green P, Hernández-Pinzón I, Hubbard A, Moscou MJ (2015) The development of quick, robust, quantitative phenotypic assays for describing the host–nonhost landscape to stripe rust. *Frontiers in Plant Science* 6:876
- Dawson AM, Ferguson JN, Gardiner M, Green P, Hubbard A, Moscou MJ (2016) Isolation and fine mapping of Rps6: an intermediate host resistance gene in barley to wheat stripe rust. *Theoretical and Applied Genetics* 129:831-843
- Devadas R, Simpfendorfer S, Backhouse D, Lamb DW (2014) Effect of stripe rust on the yield response of wheat to nitrogen. *The Crop Journal* 2:201-206
- Derevnina L, Zhou M, Singh D, Wellings CR, Park RF (2015) The genetic basis of resistance to barley grass yellow rust (*Puccinia striiformis* f. sp. *pseudo-hordei*) in Australian barley cultivars. *Theoretical and Applied Genetics* 128:187-197
- Du Y, Stegmann M, Misas Villamil JC (2016) The apoplast as battleground for plant–microbe interactions. *New Phytologist* 209:34-38

- Dodds PN, Rathjen JP (2010) Plant immunity: towards an integrated view of plant–pathogen interactions. *Nature Reviews Genetics* 11:539-548
- Ellis J, Dodds P, Pryor T (2000) Structure, function and evolution of plant disease resistance genes. *Current Opinion in Plant Biology* 3:278-284
- Ellis JG, Lagudah E, Spielmeier W, Dodds P (2014) The past, present and future of breeding rust resistant wheat. *Frontiers in Plant Science* 5
- Eriksson J (1894) Ueber die specialisirung des parasitismus bei den getreiderostpilzen. *Ber Dtsch Bot Ges* 12:292-331
- Flor HH (1971) Current Status of the Gene-For-Gene Concept. *Annual Review of Phytopathology* 9:275-296
- Fluch S, Kopecky D, Burg K, Šimková H, Taudien S, Petzold A, Kubaláková M, Platzer M, Berenyi M, Krainer S, Doležel J, Lelley T (2012) Sequence Composition and Gene Content of the Short Arm of Rye (*Secale cereale*) Chromosome 1. *PLoS ONE* 7:e30784
- Fu D, Uauy C, Distelfeld A, Blechl A, Epstein L, Chen X, Sela H, Fahima T, Dubcovsky J (2009) A novel kinase-START gene confers temperature-dependent resistance to wheat stripe rust. *Science (New York, NY)* 323:1357-1360
- Garnica DP, Nemri A, Upadhyaya NM, Rathjen JP, Dodds PN (2014) The Ins and Outs of Rust Haustoria. *PLoS Pathog* 10:e1004329
- Gilbert GS, Webb CO (2007) Phylogenetic signal in plant pathogen–host range. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences* 104:4979-4983
- Gill US, Lee S, Mysore KS (2015) Host Versus Nonhost Resistance: Distinct Wars with Similar Arsenals. *Phytopathology* 105:580-587

- Greeff C, Roux M, Mundy J, Petersen M (2012) Receptor-like kinase complexes in plant innate immunity. *Frontiers in Plant Science* 3:209
- Green GJ (1966) Stem Rust of Wheat, Rye and Barley in Canada in 1965. *Canadian Plant Disease Survey* 46:27-32
- Hammond-Kosack KE, Jones JDG (1997) Plant Disease Resistance Genes. *Annual Review of Plant Physiology and Plant Molecular Biology* 48:575-607
- Heath MC (2000) Nonhost resistance and nonspecific plant defenses. *Current Opinion in Plant Biology* 3:315-319
- Huang P-Y, Zimmerli L (2014) Enhancing crop innate immunity: new promising trends. *Frontiers in Plant Science* 5:624
- Hubbard A, Lewis CM, Yoshida K, Ramirez-Gonzalez RH, de Vallavieille-Pope C, Thomas J, Kamoun S, Bayles R, Uauy C, Saunders DG (2015) Field pathogenomics reveals the emergence of a diverse wheat yellow rust population. *Genome Biology* 16:1-15
- Horvath H, Rostoks N, Brueggeman R, Steffenson B, von Wettstein D, Kleinhofs A (2003) Genetically engineered stem rust resistance in barley using the Rpg1 gene. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences of the United States of America* 100:364-369
- Hospital F (2005) Selection in backcross programmes. *Philosophical Transactions of the Royal Society B: Biological Sciences* 360:1503-1511
- Hovmøller MS (2007) Sources of seedling and adult plant resistance to *Puccinia striiformis* f.sp. *tritici* in European wheats. *Plant Breeding* 126:225-233

- Hovmøller MS, Walter S, Justesen AF (2010) Escalating Threat of Wheat Rusts. *Science* 329:369-369
- Hovmøller MS, Sørensen CK, Walter S, Justesen AF (2011) Diversity of *Puccinia striiformis* on Cereals and Grasses. *Annual Review of Phytopathology* 49:197-217
- Hovmøller MS, Walter S, Bayles RA, Hubbard A, Flath K, Sommerfeldt N, Leconte M, Czembor P, Rodriguez-Algaba J, Thach T, Hansen JG, Lassen P, Justesen AF, Ali S, de Vallavieille-Pope C (2016) Replacement of the European wheat yellow rust population by new races from the centre of diversity in the near-Himalayan region. *Plant Pathology* 65:402-411
- IBGSC (2012) A physical, genetic and functional sequence assembly of the barley genome. *Nature* 491:711-716
- Inukai T, Vales MI, Hori K, Sato K, Hayes PM (2006) RMo1 Confers Blast Resistance in Barley and Is Located within the Complex of Resistance Genes Containing Mla, a Powdery Mildew Resistance Gene. *Molecular Plant-Microbe Interactions* 19:1034-1041
- Islam AKMR, Shepherd KW, Sparrow DHB (1981) Isolation and characterization of euplasmic wheat-barley chromosome addition lines. *Heredity* 46:161-174
- IWGSC, (2014) A chromosome-based draft sequence of the hexaploid bread wheat (*Triticum aestivum*) genome. *Science* 345
- Jin Y, Szabo LJ, Carson M (2010) Century-Old Mystery of *Puccinia striiformis* Life History Solved with the Identification of *Berberis* as an Alternate Host. *Phytopathology* 100:432-435

Johnson R (1981) Durable Resistance: Definition of, Genetic Control, and Attainment in Plant Breeding. *Phytopathology* 71:567-568

Johnson R (1984) A Critical Analysis of Durable Resistance. *Annual Review of Phytopathology* 22:309-330

Jones JDG (2001) Putting knowledge of plant disease resistance genes to work. *Current Opinion in Plant Biology* 4:281-287

Jones JDG, Dangl JL (2006) The plant immune system. *Nature* 444:323-329

Jones N, Ougham H, Thomas H, Pašakinskienė I (2009) Markers and mapping revisited: finding your gene. *New Phytologist* 183:935-966

Kamino LN, Singh D, Pallotta MA, Collins NC, Park RF (2016) Mapping of seedling resistance in barley to *Puccinia striiformis* f. sp. *pseudohordei*. *Journal of Applied Genetics* 57:37-44

Kearney J (2010) Food consumption trends and drivers. *Philosophical Transactions of the Royal Society B: Biological Sciences* 365:2793-2807

Khan M, Subramaniam R, Desveaux D (2016) Of guards, decoys, baits and traps: pathogen perception in plants by type III effector sensors. *Current Opinion in Microbiology* 29:49-55

Kellogg EA (1998) Relationships of cereal crops and other grasses. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences of the United States of America* 95:2005-2010

Koebner RMD, Shepherd KW, Appels R (1986) Controlled introgression to wheat of genes from rye chromosome arm 1RS by induction of allosyndesis. *Theoretical and Applied Genetics* 73:209-217

Kitcher, K. (2016). Isolation and mapping of barley stripe rust resistance gene *RpsHOR1428-2*. *MSc Thesis*. University of East Anglia.

Kole C, Muthamilarasan M, Henry R, Edwards D, Sharma R, Abberton M, Batley J, Bentley A, Blakeney M, Bryant J, Cai H, Cakir M, Cseke LJ, Cockram J, de Oliveira AC, De Pace C, Dempewolf H, Ellison S, Gepts P, Greenland A, Hall A, Hori K, Hughes S, Humphreys MW, Iorizzo M, Ismail AM, Marshall A, Mayes S, Nguyen HT, Ogonnaya FC, Ortiz R, Paterson AH, Simon PW, Tohme J, Tuberosa R, Valliyodan B, Varshney RK, Wullschleger SD, Yano M, Prasad M (2015) Application of genomics-assisted breeding for generation of climate resilient crops: progress and prospects. *Frontiers in Plant Science* 6:563

Kolmer J (2013) Leaf Rust of Wheat: Pathogen Biology, Variation and Host Resistance. *Forests* 4:70

Krattinger SG, Lagudah ES, Wicker T, Risk JM, Ashton AR, Selter LL, Matsumoto T, Keller B (2011) Lr34 multi-pathogen resistance ABC transporter: molecular analysis of homoeologous and orthologous genes in hexaploid wheat and other grass species. *The Plant Journal* 65:392-403

Kroj T, Chanclud E, Michel-Romiti C, Grand X, Morel J-B (2016) Integration of decoy domains derived from protein targets of pathogen effectors into plant immune receptors is widespread. *New Phytologist* 210:618-626

Leonard KJ, Szabo LJ (2005) Stem rust of small grains and grasses caused by *Puccinia graminis*. *Molecular Plant Pathology* 6:99-111

- Li K, Hegarty J, Zhang C, Wan A, Wu J, Guedira GB, Chen X, Muñoz-Amatriaín M, Fu D, Dubcovsky J (2016) Fine mapping of barley locus Rps6 conferring resistance to wheat stripe rust. *Theoretical and Applied Genetics* 129:845-859
- Line RF (2002) Stripe Rust of Wheat and Barley in North America: A Retrospective Historical Review. *Annual Review of Phytopathology* 40:75-118
- Lister DL, Jones H, Jones MK, O'Sullivan DM, Cockram J (2013) Analysis of DNA polymorphism in ancient barley herbarium material: validation of the KASP SNP genotyping platform. *Taxon* 62:779-789
- Lo Iacono G, van den Bosch F, Gilligan CA (2013) Durable Resistance to Crop Pathogens: An Epidemiological Framework to Predict Risk under Uncertainty. *PLoS Comput Biol* 9:e1002870
- Lorang J, Cuesta-Marcos A, Hayes PM, Wolpert TJ (2010) Identification and mapping of adult-onset sensitivity to victorin in barley. *Molecular Breeding* 26:545-550
- Lü B, Wu J-j, Fu D-l (2015) Constructing the barley model for genetic transformation in Triticeae. *Journal of Integrative Agriculture* 14:453-468
- Macho AP, Zipfel C (2014) Plant PRRs and the Activation of Innate Immune Signaling. *Molecular Cell* 54:263-272
- Macho AP, Zipfel C (2015) Targeting of plant pattern recognition receptor-triggered immunity by bacterial type-III secretion system effectors. *Current Opinion in Microbiology* 23:14-22

- Mago R, Zhang P, Vautrin S, Šimková H, Bansal U, Luo M-C, Rouse M, Karaoglu H, Periyannan S, Kolmer J, Jin Y, Ayliffe MA, Bariana H, Park RF, McIntosh R, Doležel J, Bergès H, Spielmeyer W, Lagudah ES, Ellis JG, Dodds PN (2015) The wheat Sr50 gene reveals rich diversity at a cereal disease resistance locus. *Nature Plants* 1:15186
- Mamo BE, Smith KP, Brueggeman RS, Steffenson BJ (2014) Genetic Characterization of Resistance to Wheat Stem Rust Race TTKSK in Landrace and Wild Barley Accessions Identifies the rpg4/Rpg5 Locus. *Phytopathology* 105:99-109
- Manly KF, Cudmore RH, Meer JM (2001) Map Manager QTX, cross-platform software for genetic mapping. *Mammalian Genome* 12:930-932
- Manners J (1960) *Puccinia striiformis* Westend. var. *dactylidis* var. nov. . *Transactions of the British Mycological Society* 43:65-68
- Martis MM, Zhou R, Haseneyer G, Schmutzer T, Vrána J, Kubaláková M, König S, Kugler KG, Scholz U, Hackauf B, Korzun V, Schön C-C, Doležel J, Bauer E, Mayer KFX, Stein N (2013) Reticulate Evolution of the Rye Genome. *The Plant Cell* 25:3685-3698
- Mascher M, Schuenemann VJ, Davidovich U, Marom N, Himmelbach A, Hubner S, Korol A, David M, Reiter E, Riehl S, Schreiber M, Vohr SH, Green RE, Dawson IK, Russell J, Kilian B, Muehlbauer GJ, Waugh R, Fahima T, Krause J, Weiss E, Stein N (2016) Genomic analysis of 6,000-year-old cultivated grain illuminates the domestication history of barley. *Nature Genetics* advance online publication
- McDonald BA, Linde C (2002a) Pathogen Population Genetics, Evolutionary Potential, and Durable Resistance. *Annual Review of Phytopathology* 40:349-379

- McDonald BA, Linde C (2002b) The population genetics of plant pathogens and breeding strategies for durable resistance. *Euphytica* 124:163-180
- McDowell JM, Woffenden BJ (2003) Plant disease resistance genes: recent insights and potential applications. *Trends in Biotechnology* 21:178-183
- McNeal FH, Konzak CF, Smith EP, Tate WS, Russell TS (1971) A Uniform System for Recording and Processing Cereal Research Data Vol 3 Morries, MN: US Department of Agriculture-Agricultural Research Service ARS
- Menardo F, Praz CR, Wyder S, Ben-David R, Bourras S, Matsumae H, McNally KE, Parlange F, Riba A, Roffler S, Schaefer LK, Shimizu KK, Valenti L, Zbinden H, Wicker T, Keller B (2016) Hybridization of powdery mildew strains gives rise to pathogens on novel agricultural crop species. *Nat Genet* 48:201-205
- Miedaner T, Korzun V (2012) Marker-Assisted Selection for Disease Resistance in Wheat and Barley Breeding. *Phytopathology* 102:560-566
- Middleton CP, Senerchia N, Stein N, Akhunov ED, Keller B, Wicker T, Kilian B (2014) Sequencing of Chloroplast Genomes from Wheat, Barley, Rye and Their Relatives Provides a Detailed Insight into the Evolution of the Triticeae Tribe. *PLoS ONE* 9:e85761
- Molnár-Láng M, Linc G, Szakács É (2014) Wheat–barley hybridization: the last 40 years. *Euphytica* 195:315-329
- Monaghan J, Zipfel C (2012) Plant pattern recognition receptor complexes at the plasma membrane. *Current Opinion in Plant Biology* 15:349-357

Moore G, Devos KM, Wang Z, Gale MD (1995) Cereal Genome Evolution: Grasses, line up and form a circle. *Current Biology* 5:737-739

Moseman JG (1972) Isogenic barley lines for reaction to *Erysiphe graminis* f.sp. *hordei*. *Crop Science* 12:681-682

Mundt CC (2014) Durable resistance: A key to sustainable management of pathogens and pests. *Infection, Genetics and Evolution* 27:446-455

Muñoz-Amatriaín M, Moscou MJ, Bhat PR, Svensson JT, Bartoš J, Suchánková P, Šimková H, Endo TR, Fenton RD, Lonardi S, Castillo AM, Chao S, Cistué L, Cuesta-Marcos A, Forrest KL, Hayden MJ, Hayes PM, Horsley RD, Makoto K, Moody D, Sato K, Vallés MP, Wulff BHH, Muehlbauer GJ, Doležel J, Close TJ. (2011) An improved consensus linkage map of barley based on flow-sorted chromosomes and single nucleotide polymorphism markers. *Plant Genome* 4:238-249

Niks RE, Alemu SK, Marcel TC, van Heyzen S (2015) Mapping genes in barley for resistance to *Puccinia coronata* from couch grass and to *P. striiformis* from brome, wheat and barley. *Euphytica* 206:487-499

Niks RE, Marcel TC (2009) Nonhost and basal resistance: how to explain specificity? *New Phytologist* 182:817-828

Niu YC, Li ZQ, Shang HS (1991) *Puccinia striiformis* West. f. sp. *leymi* and f. sp. *elymi*, two new formae speciales. *Acta Univ Agric Boreali Occident* 19:58-62

Nover I, Scholz F (1969) Genetic studies on the resistance of barley yellow rust (*Puccinia striiformis* West.). *Theoretical and Applied Genetics* 39:150-155

- Oerke E-C (2006) Crop losses to pests. *The Journal of Agricultural Science* 144:31-43
- Pahalawatta V, Chen X (2005) Inheritance and Molecular Mapping of Barley Genes
Conferring Resistance to Wheat Stripe Rust. *Phytopathology* 95:884-889
- Palloix A, Ayme V, Moury B (2009) Durability of plant major resistance genes to pathogens
depends on the genetic background, experimental evidence and consequences for
breeding strategies. *New Phytologist* 183:190-199
- Pallotta M, Warner P, Fox R, Kuchel H, Jefferies S, Langridge P (2003) Marker assisted wheat
breeding in the southern region of Australia. *Proceedings of the Tenth International
Wheat Genetics Symposium (1-6 September, 2003, Paestum, Italy):789-791*
- Parry MAJ, Hawkesford MJ (2010) Food security: increasing yield and improving resource
use efficiency. *Proceedings of the Nutrition Society* 69:592-600
- Paterson AH, Bowers JE, Peterson DG, Estill JC, Chapman BA (2003) Structure and evolution
of cereal genomes. *Current Opinion in Genetics & Development* 13:644-650
- Pea G, Aung HH, Frascaroli E, Landi P, Pè EM (2013) Extensive genomic characterization of a
set of near-isogenic lines for heterotic QTL in maize (*Zea mays* L.). *BMC Genomics*
14:1-15
- Periyannan S, Moore J, Ayliffe M, Bansal U, Wang X, Huang L, Deal K, Luo M, Kong X, Bariana
H, Mago R, McIntosh R, Dodds P, Dvorak J, Lagudah E (2013) The Gene Sr33, an
Ortholog of Barley Mla Genes, Encodes Resistance to Wheat Stem Rust Race Ug99.
Science 341:786-788
- Pink DAC (2002) Strategies using genes for non-durable disease resistance. *Euphytica*
124:227-236

- Piquerez SJM, Harvey SE, Beynon JL, Ntoukakis V (2014) Improving crop disease resistance: lessons from research on Arabidopsis and tomato. *Frontiers in Plant Science* 5:671
- Poland JA, Balint-Kurti PJ, Wissler RJ, Pratt RC, Nelson RJ (2009) Shades of gray: the world of quantitative disease resistance. *Trends in Plant Science* 14:21-29
- Rae SJ, Macaulay M, Ramsay L, Leigh F, Matthews D, O'Sullivan DM, Donini P, Morris PC, Powell W, Marshall DF, Waugh R, Thomas WTB (2007) Molecular barley breeding. *Euphytica* 158:295-303
- Rommens CM, Haring MA, Swords K, Davies HV, Belknap WR (2007) The intragenic approach as a new extension to traditional plant breeding. *Trends in Plant Science* 12:397-403
- Safavi SA, Jahani-Jelodar Y, Ebrahimnejad S (2013a) Virulence patterns of barley yellow rust and effective resistance genes to *Puccinia striiformis* in three parts of Iran. *Archives of Phytopathology and Plant Protection* 46:903-910
- Safavi SA, Ahari Assadollah B, Afshari F, Arzanlou M (2013b) Slow Rusting Resistance in Iranian Barley Cultivars to *Puccinia striiformis* F. Sp. *Hordei*. *Journal of Plant Protection Research*, p 5
- Salamini F, Ozkan H, Brandolini A, Schafer-Pregl R, Martin W (2002) Genetics and geography of wild cereal domestication in the near east. *Nat Rev Genet* 3:429-441

- Salse J, Chagué V, Bolot S, Magdelenat G, Huneau C, Pont C, Belcram H, Couloux A, Gardais S, Evrard A, Segurens B, Charles M, Ravel C, Samain S, Charmet G, Boudet N, Chalhou B (2008) New insights into the origin of the B genome of hexaploid wheat: Evolutionary relationships at the SPA genomic region with the S genome of the diploid relative *Aegilops speltoides*. *BMC Genomics* 9:555-555
- Sarwar MH, Sarwar MF, Sarwar M, Qadri NA, Moghal S (2013) The importance of cereals (Poaceae: Gramineae) nutrition in human health: A review. *Journal of Cereals and Oilseeds* 4:32-35
- Schönfeld M, Ragni A, Fischbeck G, Jahoor A (1996) RFLP mapping of three new loci for resistance genes to powdery mildew (*Erysiphe graminis* f. sp. *hordei*) in barley. *Theoretical and Applied Genetics* 93:48-56
- Semagn K, Babu R, Hearne S, Olsen M (2014) Single nucleotide polymorphism genotyping using Kompetitive Allele Specific PCR (KASP): overview of the technology and its application in crop improvement. *Molecular Breeding* 33:1-14
- Senthil-Kumar M, Mysore KS (2013) Nonhost Resistance Against Bacterial Pathogens: Retrospectives and Prospects. *Annual Review of Phytopathology* 51:407-427
- Sharma TR, Das A, Thakur S, Jalali BL (2014) Recent Understanding on Structure, Function and Evolution of Plant Disease Resistance Genes. . *Proceedings of Indian National Science Academy* 80:83-93
- Shewry PR (2009) Wheat. *Journal of Experimental Botany* 60:1537-1553
- Singh RP, Hodson DP, Huerta-Espino J, Jin Y, Njau P, Wanyera R, Herrera-Foessel SA, Ward RW (2008) Will Stem Rust Destroy the World's Wheat Crop? *Advances in Agronomy*. Academic Press, pp 271-309

- Soltis ED, Soltis PS (2000) Contributions of plant molecular systematics to studies of molecular evolution. *Plant Molecular Biology* 42:45-75
- St.Clair DA (2010) Quantitative Disease Resistance and Quantitative Resistance Loci in Breeding. *Annual Review of Phytopathology* 48:247-268
- Stewart CN, Via LE (1993) A rapid CTAB DNA isolation technique useful for RAPD fingerprinting and other PCR applications. *Biotechniques* 14:748-750
- Strange RN, Scott PR (2005) Plant Disease: A Threat to Global Food Security. *Annual Review of Phytopathology* 43:83-116
- Sukarta OCA, Slootweg EJ, Goverse A (2016) Structure-informed insights for NLR functioning in plant immunity. *Seminars in Cell & Developmental Biology* 56:134-149
- Swanston JS, Newton AC, Guy DC, Gacek ES (2000) Malting Performance of Barley Cultivar Mixtures from the UK and Poland. *Journal of the Institute of Brewing* 106:239-244
- Tang D, Zhou J-M (2016) PEPRs spice up plant immunity. *The EMBO Journal* 35:4-5
- Tang J, Ohyama K, Kawaura K, Hashinokuchi H, Kamiya Y, Suzuki M, Muranaka T, Ogihara Y (2011) A New Insight into Application for Barley Chromosome Addition Lines of Common Wheat: Achievement of Stigmasterol Accumulation. *Plant Physiology* 157:1555-1567
- Tanksley SD, McCouch SR (1997) Seed Banks and Molecular Maps: Unlocking Genetic Potential from the Wild. *Science* 277:1063-1066
- Thordal-Christensen H (2003) Fresh insights into processes of nonhost resistance. *Current Opinion in Plant Biology* 6:351-357

- Tollenaar H (1967) A comparison of *Puccinia striiformis* f. sp. *poae* on bluegrass with *P. striiformis* f. sp. *tritici* and f. sp. *dactylidis*. . Phytopathology 57:418-420
- Tosa Y (1989) Genetic-analysis of avirulence of wheatgrass powdery mildew fungus on common wheat. Genome 32:913-917
- Tosa Y (1992) A Model for the Evolution of *Formae Speciales* and Races. Phytopathology 28:728-729
- Thomma BPHJ, Nürnberger T, Joosten MHAJ (2011) Of PAMPs and Effectors: The Blurred PTI-ETI Dichotomy. The Plant Cell 23:4-15
- Türkösi E, Cseh A, Darkó É, Molnár-Láng M (2016) Addition of Manas barley chromosome arms to the hexaploid wheat genome. BMC Genetics 17:87
- Türkösi E, Farkas A, Aranyi NR, Hoffmann B, Tóth V, Molnár-Láng M (2014) Improvement of the agronomic traits of a wheat–barley centric fusion by introgressing the 3HS.3BL translocation into a modern wheat cultivar. Genome 57:601-607
- Van Der Biezen EA, Jones JDG (1998) Plant disease-resistance proteins and the gene-for-gene concept. Trends in Biochemical Sciences 23:454-456
- van der Hoorn RAL, Kamoun S (2008) From Guard to Decoy: A New Model for Perception of Plant Pathogen Effectors. The Plant Cell 20:2009-2017
- van Ooijen J (2006) JoinMap 4. Software for the calculation of genetic linkage maps in experimental populations. Wageningen: Kyazma BV
- Váry Z, Mullins E, McElwain JC, Doohan FM (2015) The severity of wheat diseases increases when plants and pathogens are acclimatized to elevated carbon dioxide. Global Change Biology 21:2661-2669

Walter S, Ali S, Kemen E, Nazari K, Bahri BA, Enjalbert J, Hansen JG, Brown JKM, Sicheritz-

Pontén T, Jones J, de Vallavieille-Pope C, Hovmøller MS, Justesen AF (2016) Molecular markers for tracking the origin and worldwide distribution of invasive strains of *Puccinia striiformis*. *Ecology and Evolution* 6:2790-2804

Wei F, Gobelman-Werner K, Morroll SM, Kurth J, Mao L, Wing R, Leister D, Schulze-Lefert P,

Wise RP (1999) The Mla (powdery mildew) resistance cluster is associated with three NBS-LRR gene families and suppressed recombination within a 240-kb DNA interval on chromosome 5S (1HS) of barley. *Genetics* 153:1929-1948

Weiss E, Kislev ME, Hartmann A (2006) Autonomous Cultivation Before Domestication.

Science 312:1608-1610

Wellings CR (2011) Global status of stripe rust: a review of historical and current threats.

Euphytica 179:129-141

Wellings CR, Burdon JJ, McIntosh RA, Wallwork H, Raman H, Murray GM (2000) A new

variant of *Puccinia striiformis* causing stripe rust on barley and wild *Hordeum* species in Australia. *Plant Pathology* 49:803-803

Wiebe GA (1934) Complementary factors in barley giving lethoal progeny. *Journal of*

Heredity 25:273-274

Win J, Chaparro-Garcia A, Belhaj K, Saunders DGO, Yoshida K, Dong S, Schornack S, Zipfel C,

Robatzek S, Hogenhout SA, Kamoun S (2012) Effector Biology of Plant-Associated

Organisms: Concepts and Perspectives. *Cold Spring Harbor Symposia on Quantitative*

Biology 77:235-247

- Wolfe MS (1985) The Current Status and Prospects of Multiline Cultivars and Variety Mixtures for Disease Resistance. *Annual Review of Phytopathology* 23:251-273
- Yan GP, Chen XM (2006) Molecular mapping of a recessive gene for resistance to stripe rust in barley. *Theoretical and Applied Genetics* 113:529-537
- Yan G, Chen X (2007a) Molecular Mapping of the rps1.a Recessive Gene for Resistance to Stripe Rust in BBA 2890 Barley. *Phytopathology* 97:668-673
- Yan G, Chen X (2007b) Identification of a Quantitative Trait Locus for High-Temperature Adult-Plant Resistance Against *Puccinia striiformis* f. sp. *hordei* in 'Bancroft' Barley. *Phytopathology* 98:120-127
- Zhu Y, Qian W, Hua J (2010) Temperature Modulates Plant Defense Responses through NB-LRR Proteins. *PLoS Pathog* 6:e1000844
- Zipfel C (2009) Early molecular events in PAMP-triggered immunity. *Current Opinion in Plant Biology* 12:414-420